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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
DEP	Digital Europe Programme
DMS	Document Management System
DTPC	Deputy Technical Project Coordinator
EAG	External Advisory Group
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FACL	Financial & Administrative Coordinator Leader
GA	Grant Agreement
KOM	Kick-off meeting
LCMS	Learning Content Management System
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
NEB	New European Bauhaus
PMB	Project Management Board
R&I	Research and Innovation
SG	Stakeholder Group
The Consortium	All the Project Partners, viz. TU DELFT + Trust-IT + COMMpla + EAAE + ICF + IW
The Project Beneficiaries	The signatory Partners of the Grant Agreement, viz. TU DELFT + Trust-IT + EAAE + ICF + IW
TL	Task Leader
TPC	Technical Project Coordinator
TWG	Technical Working Group
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Keywords

Community, engagement, platform, multidisciplinary, stakeholder, engagement, risk, responsibility

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Executive Summary

The digiNEB.eu project supports the New European Bauhaus initiative (NEB) by creating synergies with EU technological innovation, particularly technologies that support Smart Communities and the implementation of the Green Deal. This document outlines the Early Adopters Network for national and regional adoption of the digiNEB.eu project. It defines Early Adopters as stakeholders who have actively and positively engaged with digital strategies for NEB projects, Smart Communities, or NEB-aligned initiatives. They are distinct from "users" in that they are likely to encourage and promote the use of these strategies among colleagues and peers, as well as provide feedback and contribute expert knowledge that may lead to improvements in the systems implemented.

The first strategy for stakeholder engagement aims to onboard key community leaders from target NEB and Smart Communities projects via in-person engagement. This strategy has already been implemented by first identifying gaps and synergies in NEB and Smart Communities engagement, and then by addressing them with the first in-person Early Adopter onboarding event NEB@CERN. The event was conceived as a high-level co-creation lab focusing on digitally-enabled approaches to sustainability, inclusion and aesthetics and combined inspirational talks with 'think and do tanks' – co-creation sessions focusing on digiNEB priority topics. These included the new NEB Academy for a sustainable built environment, and synergies between NEB and digital with multidisciplinary Smart Communities. The NEB@CERN event resulted in multiple achievements and impacts. It created a new hybrid community between the digital Smart Communities projects and NEB, resulting in the creation of the digiNEB Early Adopter Network. The network has started to collaborate on a White Paper covering topics such as mission-oriented learning, closed-loop materials lifecycles, and design for regional ecosystems framework conditions. The community has agreed that the NEB Lighthouses will now host the community on a regular basis. Thematic Working Groups have been established to organise the collaborative White Paper, and further activities are planned as part of the TWG onboarding strategy.

The second strategy is to develop further the Early Adopters Network by focusing in greater detail on common missions through Thematic Working Groups (TWGs), contributions to the digiNEB White Paper and the development of TWG-related thematic events. The digiNEB.eu project has agreed to replace "Technical Working Groups" with "Thematic Working Groups" to encourage broader participation by the NEB stakeholders. Thematic Working Groups have been established through co-creation by the digiNEB.eu community at the NEB@CERN event and updated with the latest NEB agenda for the NEB Academy. Onboarding of further TWG members will be done through curated matchmaking between leading NEB contributors and digital innovation project owners.

The third Early Adopter engagement strategy focuses on the onboarding of NEB stakeholders from the European Regions by means of a Regional Innovation Model. The strategy leverages background work completed as part of NEB High Level Round Table activities during 2022 together with the European Committee of the Regions, in a collaboration with Commissioner Ferreira's Cohesion Funds and INTERREG Europe, as well as best practice from pioneering and early successes of NEB regional initiatives. The adopted joint proposal by Michela Magas and the European Committee of the Regions focuses on a Regional Innovation Model that implements an ecosystemic approach to EU funds by connecting existing funding mechanisms, such as Interreg Europe and Cohesion Funds, to create a large-scale value network and multiplier effect for local and regional sustainability innovation activities. In digiNEB this proposal is being combined with best practice from successful NEB initiatives such as Sweden's National NEB project "Visions in the North" and the related digiNEB

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Early Adopter Duved project. Best practice content for the Regional Innovation Model combines tools and methods for community innovation that will be disseminated to regional Early Adopters. The Regional Innovation Model Handbook is being drafted as a guide for implementing best practices across various regional ecosystems. The combined Regional Innovation Model implementing innovative processes on the ground and scaling resulting innovations from the ground up via linked funding mechanisms, is expected to create wide-reaching impacts on regional ecosystems, including pilot solutions for circular models, environments that stimulate co-creation, behavioural shifts and system change. A first working draft of the RIM Handbook is included as this report's Annexe.

The fourth strategy for Early Adopter engagement focuses on onboarding through social media, webinars and success stories. The strategy involves cross-promotion and content sharing between the website and social media channels, audience engagement through interactive activities, and a specific campaign dedicated for building an Early Adopter Network. The implementation of this strategy involves the creation of an Early Adopter application form, dedicated web pages for onboarded Early Adopters, events with Early Adopters, and a pay-per-click campaign. The success of the strategy relies on the creation of meaningful content and entry points for the early adopters on the digiNEB.eu platform.

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1. Introduction

Upon instruction by the President von der Leyen's NEB Advisor Ruth Reichstein, the Champions Network has been renamed 'the Early Adopter Network'.

We define a digiNEB 'Early Adopter' as a stakeholder who has actively and positively engaged with digital strategies for NEB projects, Smart Communities or NEB-aligned initiatives. An Early Adopter is distinct from a 'user' in that they are likely to encourage and promote the use of these strategies amongst colleagues and peers, as well as provide feedback and contribute expert knowledge that may lead to improvements in the systems implemented.

This deliverable describes the Early Adopters Network programme, its engagement process and the communication and outreach activities that the task is undertaking to ensure engagement across the EU regions, reporting on achievements and lessons learned.

The related task supports and encourages the creation of a digiNEB Early Adopter Network and facilitates connections with national and regional initiatives through scouting and recruiting of digiNEB Early Adopters. The task develops several strategies to leverage close alliances with the EAG, NEB Partners, NEB HLRT and Friends of NEB, as well as members of Interreg Europe, the Regional Governments managing Cohesion Funds, and the EAAE network. The onboarding strategies are designed to highlight Early Adopter success stories and best practice. The dissemination strategy includes the management of the Early Adopter Network through dedicated pages in the digiNEB.eu (<http://digiNEB.eu/>) platform; a press release, several news pieces, newsletters and direct email marketing campaigns to keep the stakeholder community up to date; and the organisation of webinars featuring Early Adopter success stories and best practice.

2. Strategy 1: Onboarding via in-person engagement with key community leaders

2.1.Planning: Early Adopter Curation

This strategy focuses on onboarding Early Adopters via in-person interaction. The first large-scale in-person interaction, NEB@CERN, was conceived as a high-level co-creation lab focusing on digitally-enabled approaches to sustainability, inclusion and aesthetics. The event was hosted by **CERN IdeaSquare**, who focus on methodologies for experimental innovation and learning through doing. CERN has also launched the CERN Green Village where they offer residencies to EU projects engaged with the Green Deal.

The event was curated by Michela Magas, Member of President von der Leyen's [High Level Round Table for the New European Bauhaus](#), Member of the Advisory Board of CERN ISAB-G, and Lead for project partner ICF.

2.1.1. Developing an Early Adopter Network (previously 'Champions Network')

In order to create an Early Adopter Network, we first **identified several gaps in community interaction**, both within NEB and Smart Communities.

- **Lighthouse projects**

Recently, NEB has funded six Lighthouse projects. Since their launch, these projects have not had an opportunity to collaborate and leverage synergies:

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- **CULTUURCAMPUS:** A sustainable hub of arts, research, learning and community as a catalyst. By blending education, research, policy, and culture and considering the lived experiences of its residents, Cultuurcampus aims to transform the disadvantaged urban area of Rotterdam South (NL). The Cultuurcampus will be in a historic building and act as a hub for different groups and activities. (<https://www.cultuurencampusrotterdam.nl/en/>)
 - **NEB-STAR** (New European Bauhaus STAvanger): NEB-STAR will showcase how territorial transformation plans can incorporate the principles and values of the NEB in Stavanger (NO), Prague (CZ) and Utrecht (NL). The project will tackle four emblematic challenges linked to climate-neutral cities, all considering local needs and concerns through co-creation with residents and stakeholders. (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079952>)
 - **NEBourhoods:** NEBourhoods prepares Munich-Neuperlach (DE) for the future as mapped out by the European Green Deal regarding the built environment, circularity, mobility, energy, food, and health. The project will build on the area's strengths – a strong sense of community, vast green areas, and large-scale housing, even if in need of renovation – and address its weaknesses – higher than average unemployment and lower than average education levels. (<https://www.nebourhoods.de/>)
 - **DESIRE** (Designing the Irresistible Circular Society): the project wants to tackle the major challenges faced by societies and cities: climate change, biodiversity loss and resource challenges. Based on three main themes of inclusivity, circularity and reconciling cities with nature, the project will use art, architecture, and design to explore alternative ways of transforming territories across different European cities in Denmark, the Netherlands, Italy, Latvia and Slovenia. (<https://www.irresistiblecircularsociety.eu/>)
 - **EHHUR** (EYES HEARTS HANDS Urban Revolution): the project supports cities and vulnerable residents in transforming their built environment. Spread across seven different locations in the EU and Associated Countries (Denmark, Belgium, Portugal, Italy, Greece, Turkey, and Croatia), it will seek to tackle socioeconomic and cultural challenges such as social segregation, energy poverty, and degradation of depopulated historical centres. (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079948>)
 - **Bauhaus of the Seas Sails:** the project aims to promote renewed ethical and aesthetic regenerative development from a diverse range of dimensions of our continued relationship with the sea. Conceived as a journey with Portugal as a starting point, the Bauhaus of the Seas will generate a design movement extending to all European coastal and maritime regions.
- **NEB Lab Projects**
Newly-funded NEB Projects have never interacted with the NEB projects established in the first two years of the initiative, including:
 - [NEB Goes South](#)
 - the [New European Bauhaus of the Mountains](#)
 - [Nordic Carbon Neutral Bauhaus](#)
 - the [Friends of NEB](#)
 - the [NEB High Level Round Table](#)
 - **Smart Communities**
NEB projects have never interacted with the Smart Communities and Smart Cities projects such as:

- o [DS4SSCC](#) (Data Space for Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities) is an EU-funded initiative that prepares for the creation of a data space for smart communities as an enabler of the EU Green Deal goals and Sustainable Development Goals.
- o [Living in EU](#): through co-creation with citizens, the project aims to bring the economic and social benefits of this transformation to all local communities and implement an inclusive digital Europe with powerful digital services, technologies, infrastructures and skills).
- o [AURORAL](#): Architecture for Unified Regional and Open digital ecosystems for Smart Communities and Rural Areas Large scale applications.
- o [DUET](#): Virtual city replicas that make it easy to understand the complex interrelation between traffic, air quality, noise and other urban factors. Powerful analytics model the expected impacts of potential change to aid evidence-based operational decisions and longer-term policy choices.
- o [CommunityCity](#): A transformative citizen-centred project that will launch 100 tech pilots addressing the needs of cities and communities through co-creation and co-learning processes.
- o [CrAft](#): Part of the New European Bauhaus initiative that will place the transition to climate neutrality at the heart of urban stakeholders. The project supports the Mission Board on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities and the NetZeroCities platform in designing and deploying Climate City Contracts based on knowledge from CrAft's 3 Sandbox Cities (Bologna, Prague, and Amsterdam) and 60 CrAft Reference Cities.
- **digiNEB External Advisory Group**
The digiNEB EAG, including members of the NEB HLRT have never had a chance to collaborate with the NEB Lighthouses, or identify synergies with Smart Communities. These include esteemed members of the digiNEB EAG:
 - o **Matti Kuittinen**, a representative of the Finnish Ministry of the Environment and Chair of the Nordic Carbon-Neutral Bauhaus;
 - o **José Pedro Sousa**, Professor at FAUP, University of Porto, co-founder of Bauhaus Goes South;
 - o **Mia Roth-Cerina**, Vice-Dean of the Faculty of Architecture at the University of Zagreb, co-founder of Bauhaus Goes South;
 - o **Tom Minderhoud**, Partner at UN Studio
- **CERN** Several CERN Green, Sustainable and Community initiatives have never had the chance to interact with the NEB Community or the Smart Communities, including:
 - o **CERN Green Village**: The Site and Civil Engineering (SCE) Department manages and develops CERN's real estate assets and infrastructures in agreement with CERN's scientific strategy, as well as all the services related to the caretaking and operation of the CERN site. Its vision is to create an inspiring and welcoming environment for CERN's scientific community now and in the future. With this vision in mind it has launched projects on sustainable design, construction & operation that aim to reduce gas & electricity consumption on campus operations by 5%, increase the positive impact on CERN's community & the environment, and create a Green Village within the CERN Campus where breakthrough technologies for sustainability can be tested. The CERN Green Village offers an agile and flexible village-size laboratory, an

ideation and experimentation space, a platform for engagement with young innovators, and a showcase for innovation and societal engagement.

- o **CERN IdeaSquare:** IdeaSquare aligns with and supports CERN's mission. Its specific focus is on offering a platform for early-stage collaboration between students, scientists, other CERN personnel and relevant organisations across disciplines. IdeaSquare raises interest in CERN beyond the purely scientific discovery. The activities carried out at IdeaSquare tie science innovation to SDGs and to a better future of our society. 12 activities intervene at the early stage of the innovation chain — what is known as the Fuzzy Front End of the R&D&I process. The processes we propose and develop trigger transformations in the way we think about societal challenges and prompt us to identify solutions that will have a real impact on people's lives. IdeaSquare raises interest in CERN beyond the purely scientific discovery. The activities carried out at IdeaSquare tie science innovation to the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and work towards laying out a better future for our society.

The development consisted of **closing the above gaps** by bringing all of the above stakeholders together in person at a 2.5-day knowledge exchange workshop and identifying synergies between the individual groups.

2.1.2. Securing Stakeholder Engagement

Resource management strategy

The need for such a large community event, matched with the limited project budget, required collaboration and colocation with strategic project partners. digiNEB funds focused on delivery of content in line with the DoA and community synergies. A collaborative effort resulted in **match funding** from:

- A globally relevant, authoritative scientific research host venue
- Individually-funded community projects from NEB and Smart Communities
- digiNEB funds for partner and EAG travel

Community management strategy

Community management was conducted by event curator Michela Magas in close collaboration with the CERN IdeaSquare team. The following **strategies for securing engagement** were deployed:

- The event was curated as a high-level meeting limited to 50 participants on an invitation-only basis.
- Invitations were to project leaders and influencers who represented broader digital and NEB communities.
- Individual meetings with each invited stakeholder to discuss their priorities with respect to NEB and digital.
- Special invitations were issued by CERN for those who required an official invitation, including EU officials.
- Individual scheduling and design of topics for discussion based on participants' and project priorities.
- Correspondence and briefing regarding the new NEB directions: NEB Academy and NEB and digital.

- Catering to individual needs, with special arrangements for accommodation at the CERN Hostel for low project budgets.
- Full catering including care of dietary requirements was provided by CERN.

2.1.3. Identifying Synergies with NEB

By aligning individual and project priorities through curation, programming and facilitation of the in-person event, it was possible to group and engage the stakeholders in joint missions that reflect and advance the NEB priorities.

Synergies were identified between:

- NEB projects and Smart Communities
- NEB Lighthouse project missions and ambitions for the use of digital tools
- NEB Academy and the use of digital tools
- Individual NEB stakeholders (e.g.: Lighthouse project leaders, EAG members, Smart Communities projects) through the use of digital tools
- CERN project development and NEB project development

2.1.4. Designing KPIs for Early Adopter Engagement

For the successful onboarding of Early Adopters we set out several goals:

- **KPI 1:** Identify at least three major gaps in community interaction between NEB and Smart Communities.
- **KPI 2:** Identify at least three potential synergies that could arise from collaboration between digital and NEB community stakeholders
- **KPI 3:** Onboard at least 25 Early Adopters in the first six months of the project.
- **KPI 4:** Engage Early Adopters in at least one collaborative NEB-related activity resulting from in-person interaction at the first digiNEB Early Adopter event.

Figure 1 NEB@CERN multidisciplinary community

2.2.Action: First Early Adopter in-person event

The event was planned to run for 2.5 days starting on the afternoon of Monday 27th February. It combined inspirational talks with ‘think and do tanks’ – co-creation sessions focusing on the topics that included the new NEB Academy for a sustainable built environment, multidisciplinary Smart Communities, and digitally enabled beyond-human ecosystems. All participants were actively engaged in the co-creation process.

Figure 2 NEB@CERN presentation by Jan Bunge

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2.2.1. Schedule and participants

Schedule

Monday, 27 February

12:00 → **13:00**: Welcome, registration, sandwich lunch & mingling

13:00 → **14:00**: Introduction to CERN, IdeaSquare, Green Village; NEB, Academy, digiNEB

Speakers:

Mar Capeáns Garrido, CERN Green Village

Markus Nordberg, CERN IdeaSquare

Ruth Reichstein, New European Bauhaus, European Commission

Franklin van der Hoeven, Director of Research of the Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment and programme manager Open Science at TU Delft and Coordinator, digiNEB

Silvana Muscella, CEO Trust-IT and Technical Manager, digiNEB

Michela Magas, NEB@CERN curator, New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table and Advisory Board CERN ISAB-g

14:00 → **16:00**: First “think and do” session on shaping the NEB Academy lead by the Nordic Carbon Neutral Bauhaus with participation by ALL.

Introduction by **Ruth Schagemann**, President, Architects’ Council of Europe (ACE)

Moderators:

Matti Kuitinen, Senior Ministerial Advisor at the Ministry of the Environment of Finland

Helena Bjarnegård, Swedish National Architect, Swedish National Board for Housing, Building and Planning (remotely)

16:00 → **16:30**: Coffee Break

16:30 → **18:30**: Second “think and do” session on shaping the NEB Academy lead by Bauhaus Goes South with participation by ALL.

Introduction by **Oya Atalay Franck**, President, European Association of Architectural Education (EAAE)

Moderators:

Mia Roth-Čerina, Council Member of the European Association for Architectural Education and Vice-Dean for International Relations, Faculty of Architecture, University of Zagreb

José Pedro Sousa, Member of the New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table and Associate Professor at Faculty of Architecture (FAUP), University Of Porto

18:30 → **19:00**: Free Time

19:00 → **22:20**: Dinner (CERN Restaurant 2)

Tuesday, 28 February**09:00 → 09:30:** Coffee Break**09:30 → 10:30:** Meet the New European Bauhaus Lighthouse projects**Speakers:****Markus Reymann**, Bauhaus of the Seas and Director, TBA21 Academy, Ocean Space Venice**Nicole Arthur Cabrera**, Bauhaus of the Seas and TBA21 Academy, Ocean Space Venice**Dirk Ahlers**, NEB-STAR and Senior Researcher and Project Manager +CityxChange at Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)**Heather Bergsland**, NEB-STAR and Project Leader, New European Bauhaus Stavanger**Amanda Brandellero**, CULTUURCAMPUS and Associate Professor, Erasmus University Rotterdam**Martin Luce**, NEBourhoods and Director, TUM School of Engineering and Design, Technical University of Munich**Aase Højlund Nielsen**, DESIRE and Project Manager, BLOXHUB**Carlo Battisti**, Eyes Hearts Hands and President, Living Future Europe
10:30 → 12:30: Third “think and do” session on the NEB Academy**10:30 → 12:30:** Third “think and do” session on the NEB AcademyIntroduction by **Michela Magas**, NEB@CERN curator, New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table and Advisor to CERN ISAB-g**Moderators:****Jan Åman**, Author Duved and Norrlands Model**Florence Kuijl**, Communication Manager, InnovaWood**Anna Sandak**, leader in Wood Modification at the InnoRenew CoE and Associate Professor at University of Primorska**12:30 → 14:00:** Sandwich lunch 1h 30m**14:00 → 14:15:** NEB and digital: Visualising and exploring CERN’s CAD data in 3D, Virtual Reality and Digital Twins**Speaker: Jurgen de Jonghe, CERN**

During the afternoon the participants will be able to explore the CERN Accelerator and Detector Complex using VR

14:15 → 14:30 ATTRACT- European platform for breakthrough innovation**Speaker: Pablo Garcia Tello, CERN****14:30 → 15:00:** The junction between NEB and digital: Smart Communities**Speakers: Sandra Vengadasalam** (Max Planck Digital Library) and **René Ranger** (Max Planck Digital Library (MPDL))

15:00 → 16:00: Meet the Smart Communities projects

Facilitator: **Davor Meersman** (The Maximal Impact Foundation and ICF)

Speakers:

Tom Minderhoud, Architect and Associate Director, UN Studio

Andreas Rudenå, CEO, Paramountric, senior researcher BASAJAUN and digiNEB ICF

Anke Schluensen-Rico, The HuT Project and Scientific Coordinator, Climate Service Center Germany (GERICS)

16:00 → 16:30: Coffee Break

Angel Navarro, MAtchUP and Mobility Program Officer, Las Naves

Natalie Samovich, CoFounder ResilientGroup / Chair WG Energy AIOTI

Gert de Tant, CEO - Sirius NV / CTO The Maximal Impact Foundation

19:00 → 22:30: Dinner (Restaurant 2)

Wednesday, 1 March

09:00 → 09:30: Coffee Break

09:30 → 12:30: Introducing Beyond Human Ecosystems

Facilitator: **Markus Reymann**, Bauhaus of the Seas and Director, TBA21 Academy, Ocean Space Venice

Speakers:

Dan Hill, Director, Melbourne School of Design and Professor in Built Environment, Faculty of Architecture, Building and Planning, University of Melbourne

Jan Bunge, Director, Squint/Opera and contributor New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table

Jan Åman, Author Duved and Norrlands Model, ICF

12:30 → 14:00: Sandwich lunch 1h 30m

14:00 → 16:30: NEB and digital: the EU Regions and CERN

Facilitator: **Michela Magas**

Speaker:

Faezeh Abbasi, CERN

16:30 → 17:00: Coffee, Wrap Up, Conclusions

17:00 → 17:30: Bus transportation to the Airport

Figure 3 NEB@CERN participants

Participants

Name	Title / Project
NEB Flagships/Academy/digiNEB Advisory	
Ruth Reichstein	NEB Advisor to President von der Leyen I.D.E.A., European Commission
Matti Kuittinen	Senior Ministerial Advisor at the Ministry of the Environment of Finland
Helena Bjarnegård	Swedish National Architect, Swedish National Board for Housing, Building and Planning
Ruth Schagemann	President, Architects' Council of Europe (ACE)
José Pedro Sousa	Member of the New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table and Associate Professor at Faculty of Architecture (FAUP), University Of Porto
Mia Roth Čerina	Council Member of the European Association for Architectural Education and Vice-Dean for International Relations, Faculty of Architecture, University of Zagreb
Tom Minderhoud	Architect and Associate Director, UN Studio
Anna Sandak	Leader in Wood Modification at the InnoRenew CoE and Associate Professor at University of Primorsk
NEB Lab and Lighthouse Projects	
Oya Atalay Franck	President, European Association of Architectural Education (EAAE) and NEB Partner
Frank van der Hoeven	Director of Research of the Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment and programme manager Open Science at TU Delft and

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	Coordinator, digiNEB
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Carlo Battisti	Eyes Hearts Hands and President, Living Future Europe
Dan Hill	NEB Advisor and Director, Melbourne School of Design and Professor in Built Environment, Faculty of Architecture, Building and Planning, University of Melbourne
Dirk Ahlers	NEB-STAR and Senior Researcher and Project Manager +CityxChange at Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)
Martin Luce	NEBourhoods and Director, TUM School of Engineering and Design, Technical University of Munich
Heather Bergsland	NEB-STAR and Project Leader, New European Bauhaus Stavanger
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Jan Bunge	Director, Squint/Opera and contributor New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table
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Smart Communities	
Natalie Samovich	CoFounder ResilientGroup / Chair WG Energy AIOTI
Sandra Vengadasalam	Co-founder Bloxberg and Deputy Manager, Max Planck Digital Library
René Ranger	Project Owner Digital Labs, Max Planck Society
Anke Schluensen-Rico	The HuT Project and Scientific Coordinator, Climate Service Center Germany (GERICS)
Angel Navarro	MATCHUP and Mobility Program Officer, Las Naves

Andreas Rudenå	CEO, Paramountric, Senior Researcher at Industry Commons Foundation, Senior Researcher BASAJAUN and digiNEB
Davor Meersman	Executive Chairman, The Maximal Impact Foundation (MIMPACT) and Smart Communities Advisory, Industry Commons Foundation
Gert De Tant	CEO - Sirius NV / CTO The Maximal Impact Foundation
CERN	
Mar Capeans	CERN Green Village, Head of the Site and Civil Engineering (SCE) department, Particle Physicist
Markus Nordberg	Head of Resources Development of the Development and Innovation Unit (IPT-DI), Coordinator of IdeaSquare
Jurgen de Jonghe	CERN Digital Twin of the Accelerator
Pablo Garcia Tello	Section Head of the Development of EU Projects & Initiatives
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Francisca Siza	Industry Commons Foundation
Maria Giuffrida	Trust-IT
Rita Giuffrida	Trust-IT
Claudio de Majo	Trust-IT

2.2.2. NEB Academy sessions

The establishment of the NEB Academy is currently the top priority of the NEB implementation stage. As a flagship initiative of the European Year of Skills, the New European Bauhaus plans to launch the NEB Academy focusing on skills for the sustainable living environment.

The NEB Academy will provide a coherent and accessible set of online and offline training at the European scale and promote inter-regional exchange of skills and best practices. The training will be developed with stakeholders from the construction ecosystem and delivered by structures recognized as NEB Academy Hubs (e.g. universities, research centres, professional chambers) with

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learning materials managed from a digital platform and a strong digital component for the curricula, including learning of cutting edge digital tools for the green transition.

The NEB Academy sessions at NEB@CERN were therefore planned in order to engage both core NEB and Smart Communities stakeholders to respond to the digital and engagement needs of the NEB Academy.

Mapping of the preliminary community feedback

The initial NEB Academy priorities were mapped based on the preliminary information gathered by the NEB team at the European Commission from the broader NEB community. This served as the starting point for discussion and community interaction on the creation of educational tools and the use of the digital to achieve said goals. Topics included the design/planning phase for sustainable solutions with architects and engineers, the construction and renovation phase, operations and facility management, sustainable demolition, policy and building administration.

First “think and do” session on the NEB Academy

The session was introduced with a speech by Ruth Schagemann, President of the Architects’ Council of Europe (ACE). The co-creation session was designed and conducted by Matti Kuittinen from the Ministry of the Environment of Finland with Helena Bjarnegård, Swedish National Architect representing the Swedish National Board for Housing, Building and Planning.

NEB ACADEMY

The first challenge addressed the need to take NEB values into the learning process. Community feedback highlighted the need for diverse and unusual perspectives, new knowledge driven by interdisciplinarity, experience as a way to understand real values, grounding of projects in real experiences, and a **focus on shifting mindsets and behaviours**.

The second challenge asked how to enable a deeper and faster sustainability transition with the NEB Academy. The feedback was dominated by the active inclusion of diverse target groups in the education process. These included policy makers, regulators, role models, children, diverse cultures and global perspectives. Incentives included lowering the entry barrier, making the transition irresistible, raising awareness of beauty, rewarding sustainability, active engagement with democracy, adaptation and regeneration initiatives. The education pillars derived from the discussion were **'learning by doing', learning by prototyping solutions, ensuring diversity and including accessibility**.

The third challenge questioned the role of aesthetics in building new skills and mindsets. A redefinition of what is considered beautiful was requested, including finding beauty in the NEB values. Considerations of context, the time we live in, the market forces, the functions, the perception, and the unknown, both challenge and define the term of aesthetics. Opening up dialogue and creating a common ground help to define aesthetics. Considerations of diversity led to finding beauty in informal settlements and temporary structures, particularly with reference to the work by Shigeru Ban and Sheela Patel. **Experience-based aesthetics were linked to beauty that emanates out of a sense of community.**

The fourth challenge considered how to work effectively together on the NEB Academy considering its complex context. Embracing complexity was suggested by working with both nature and technology, using multidisciplinary approaches and finding common ground. This resulted in learning that is **mission-oriented, place-based, joining disciplines and working from the ground up.**

Second “think and do” session on the NEB Academy

The second NEB Academy co-creation session was introduced with a speech by Oya Atalay Franck, President of the European Association of Architectural Education (EAAE). The session was designed and conducted by the Bauhaus Goes South founders Mia Roth-Čerina, Vice-Dean of the Faculty of Architecture, University of Zagreb, and Prof. José Pedro Sousa of the Faculty of Architecture (FAUP), at the University of Porto.

The discussion started by examining what were the knowledge areas required. It proceeded by investigating how content can reflect needs, crises and policies; where does education take place; who participates in education; and where and how can different actors come together. The discussion highlighted the need to include decision makers who are not usually part of the education process; the need for place-based learning with the help of virtual environments; links between new technology and traditional knowledge; involving citizens in participatory planning; and the role of facilitators in community learning processes.

Third “think and do” session on the NEB Academy

The third NEB Academy co-creation session was introduced with a speech by Michela Magas, Member of the NEB High Level Round Table, followed by an introduction by Prof. Anna Sandak to the work of the first planned NEB Academy Hub at InnoRenew / University of Primorska, Slovenia. The session was facilitated by Florence Kuijl (InnovaWood), and Mar Muñoz Aparici (EAAE).

What are the most relevant topics to be covered by NEB academy?

GROUP 1

GROUP 2

Users that use buildings, different ways they can play with the space, ex. kids

Consider protocols and tutorials for municipalities for ways to structure projects, mia

discussion forum, how to conduct projects in a different way!!! Mia

GROUP 3

Digi NEB as a heart to connect everything, timeline that sees results regularly, use digital tools, Silvana

Interaction with society, we need to hear a vision from the academy, homepage of NEB needs to become something else, oya

Lighthouse projects give a lot

Sustainable with energies that we all have, oya

GROUP 4

IA, how to run a business, inter-cultural management

Health (indoor and outdoor)

Communication

Materials (bio-based / wood)

GROUP 5

Communication within the group, hear to communicate, consider different nationalities -> use Miro since its accessible, Tom M

Communication is key

Software packages, tools like Miro, cross discipline interoperability between architects and engineers

GROUP 6

Broaden context of academy to create new learnings, Jan A.

Connecting / networking and communication

The session covered questions such as the most relevant topics for the NEB Academy; how to attract different stakeholder groups; how to encourage more learning about biomaterials for construction; how to overcome the language barrier; what contribution would make the NEB Academy more sustainable, beautiful and inclusive; and where will the NEB Academy be in 5 and in 10 years' time. Community feedback included in a set of recommendations:

- the introduction of protocols and tutorials for municipalities on how to structure projects;
- considerations of indoor and outdoor health;
- learning inter-cultural management;
- cross-discipline communication and interoperability;
- flagship projects to learn from;
- working with industry to prototype solutions at scale;
- learning by doing.

The session concluded that **NEB should be a global academy and instigate change at a global scale.**

Figure 4: Sandra Vengadasalam of the Max Planck Digital Library presents the Bloxberg decentralised technology

2.2.3. NEB and digital

The second day of the workshop was designed to incentivise interaction, collaboration and synergies between the newly funded NEB Lighthouse projects, NEB Lab initiatives, CERN and Smart Communities projects.

A total of 15 projects were presented on the day, each allowing for interaction and identification of synergies, and closing the gaps identified in Section 2. Community interaction resulted in several proposals for collaborations and novel ideas for the use of digital technologies in NEB initiatives. Ongoing collaborations have been initiated between digiNEB partners and community members.

Figure 5: Gert de Tant, CEO Sirus NV, on the key principles behind urban technology strategies

Figure 6: Jan Åman (ICF) on scaling the Duved and Norrlands Models

2.2.4. Recommendations for the EU Regions

The third day introduced ecosystemic approaches to the junction between NEB and digital, with keynotes by Dan Hill and Jan Bunge about built and virtual environments, and community facilitation and innovation by digINEB Early Adopter Jan Åman, with particular focus on scaling best practice for the European Regions.

Recommendations were created for topics to be developed further in the followup event in Slovenia on 6-7 March, for activities in the EU Regions, and for further interaction of the NEB community with CERN. These included:

- linking all projects represented across the regions and creating a large ecosystem;
- engaging the NEB lighthouses in the creation of the NEB Academy and its ecosystem;
- creating a safe space to explore and prototype together;
- joining more artists and scientists to open up new knowledge;
- aligning local goals to have impact at large scale;
- empowering and incentivising local communities to engage in democratic processes;
- introducing open discussion fora to join civil society, industry and academia in the regions;
- moving from local government as power structure to enabler;
- understanding how spaces in cities can facilitate interaction with communities in the local context.

Recommendations were also made for the **creation of a White Paper by the newly established digINEB multidisciplinary community.**

2.2.5. Outcomes and feedback

All materials have been compiled and are accessible to the community, including community contact details (with permission), co-creation boards, presentations and media:

<https://mtflabs.notion.site/NEB-CERN-5788a61e8f4b4956a903d73a488079c9>

The feedback has been overwhelmingly positive. The following is a selection of feedback received in writing:

"Thanks again for very inspiring days at CERN!"

"It was really astonishing to meet all these interesting people with the similar vision and values for the future, everybody from his/her angle. It really gave a lot of inspiration and thoughts on how to tackle the challenges of the future."

"You managed to make the event both highly relevant, intense, inspiring and with an atmosphere of being part of something special. I brought back with me so much inspiration and so many new and relevant contacts – haven't been able to catch up with them all yet but for sure, it will have a positive influence on some parts of the (NEB Lighthouse) project."

"I will take a lot of food for thought to other communities to share. And there have been very good unexpected encounters for me during these days."

"Thousand thanks for this initiative and to have been/be part of it!"

2.2.6. Followup NEB Academy engagement

On the 6th and 7th of March 2023, an invitation-only workshop was held at the InnoRenew campus in Izola, Slovenia, taking forward the development of the NEB Academy with focus on upskilling for bio-based materials, circularity and sustainability in construction.

Uwe Kies (InnovaWood) and Michela Magas (Industry Commons Foundation) were invited to contribute as NEB Partner and Member of the NEB High Level Round Table, and were able to continue the work initiated at the NEB@CERN event on behalf of the digiNEB consortium.

Figure 7: Participants in the invitation-only NEB Academy workshop on bio-based materials, circularity and sustainability in construction

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Figure 8: One of the outcomes of the NEB Academy workshop highlights the need for validating online learning curricula with practice-based prototyping on the ground

The main takeaways from the workshop have been summarised as follows:

- It is important that NEB Academy isn't just another course, but a unique learning method that validates the knowledge acquired from online curricula with regular hands-on, collaborative, cross-disciplinary, mission-driven creative labs focused on real impacts. It should enable knowledge sharing and become a frontrunner of practice- and place-based learning based on the principles of sustainability, inclusion and aesthetics.
- Inclusion and accessibility in the living environment should feature prominently together with multiple notions of sustainability and diverse aesthetics.
- NEB Academy should include inter-regional exchange of skills & best practices and include specific skills for different regions.
- Systematic approach to identify existing gaps and needs of different target groups must be assured. Satellites of the NEB Academy or different hubs could have different main focuses that would complement each other and, in this way, assure a holistic approach to the green transition of the building sector.
- The governance structure of the NEB Academy and its operation should be able to adapt as hubs evolve. An Advisory Board should be included as part of the governance of the NEB Academy as it evolves.

2.3. Future strategy: Impacts and plans arising from the establishment of the Early Adopter Network

The NEB@CERN event achieved multiple, far reaching impacts, and set the parameters for further Early Adopter engagement.

2.3.1. Creation of the digiNEB Early Adopter Network

The event has enabled the creation of the digiNEB Early Adopter Network represented by a new hybrid community combining the digital and Smart Communities projects, NEB Lab and Lighthouse projects. This is a major Milestone for the digiNEB project and for European Commission NEB ambitions.

Individual links and synergies have been developed among the hybrid community members and further introductions to other potential Early Adopters followed. The project leaders and influencers represented at the event are now in the position to onboard their communities of stakeholders and extend the Early Adopter Network.

2.3.2. Engagement of the Early Adopters Network in the co-authorship of the digiNEB White Paper

Members of the newly established network suggested to collaborate on a White Paper relevant both for NEB and Smart Communities. The following initial topics have been suggested:

Mission-oriented learning

Learning that is not just based on best practice but joins knowledge from various disciplines to create sustainable solutions

Co-learning

- Multidisciplinary
- Trans-generational
- Public-private

Understanding value networks

- Closed-loop material lifecycles
- Keeping within the Donut Economy Model
- Digital systems for resilience and for responsibility

Design for beyond-human ecosystems

- Multi-species ecosystemic integration
- Strategies for ecosystem living
- Design for regional ecosystems framework conditions

The topics are currently being aligned with the Thematic Working Groups.

2.3.3. Regular in-person events by the NEB Lighthouse projects

The collocated event has physically galvanised all NEB projects and created a real community that wishes to collaborate from here on. NEB Lighthouses will now host the community regularly every few months. A schedule of monthly events hosted locally by individual NEB Lighthouse projects has been created in the Notion repository.

2.3.4. Collaboration between NEB and CERN

Member of CERN Management, Mar Capeans Garrido has received an invitation to proceed on 'NEBifying CERN' by Ruth Reichstein. This creates the opportunity to create the first 'NEB Beacon' for the 'NEBification' of a large research facility.

For NEBifying CERN, the community proposed on the last day a week-long prototyping event at CERN outdoors in summer, that would test ideas for sustainable, community oriented environments, together with CERN stakeholders. This event could also validate some of the learning from the NEB Academy.

2.3.5. Thematic Working Groups

Inspired by the co-creation on the NEB Academy, the event has provided the setting for a proposal for a collaborative White Paper by the newly established community. This is now being organised into several chapters by community "Thematic Working Groups". Further activities are planned as part of the TWG onboarding strategy as shown in Section 3 below.

2.4.KPIs

As per the impacts listed under Section 2.3, with the first in-person event **all of our goals for onboarding Early Adopters, set in Section 2.1.4, have been exceeded**. In addition to meeting the ambitions of WP3, the first in-person cross-domain community event **achieved Milestone MS4.1 (due in Month 9) early in the beginning of Month 6 of the project** with the first engagement and co-creation between digital R&I stakeholders and the NEB communities of practice.

Achievements resulting from the first strategy of onboarding Early Adopters include:

- 30+ Early Adopters who are project leaders and community influencers ready to be added to the digiNEB website;
- EAG members fully engaged with Early Adoption through identified synergies and co-creation and White Paper;
- CERN management staff onboarded and collaborating with NEB;
- All agreed to have their details stored in the digiNEB platform hence large addition to the digiNEB community;
- Several followup community events are being organised hosted by the individual NEB lighthouses and NEB partners;
- Each Early Adopter leads a NEB or Smart Community linked to their lighthouse or flagship projects paving the way for further adoption.

3. Strategy 2: Onboarding via Thematic Working Groups

3.1.Planning: updating TWGs in line with the NEB and Smart Communities agendas

Following the in-person event NEB@CERN (see Section 2), the plan is to finetune and amplify the starting points for Thematic Working Groups (Design & Architecture, Production & Construction, Verticals, Community & Sustainability) based on the results of co-creation by the digiNEB.eu community and focused on the most recent NEB priorities.

The newly established multidisciplinary community proposed a plan to organise work around a digiNEB White Paper so that members from diverse disciplines can jointly engage and collaborate on the content for best results.

The plan is to integrate the work on the NEB Academy with TWGs topics such as enhancing biodiversity, circularity, technologies for a sustainable construction industry, engineered biomaterials, education, participatory design processes and ending waste.

3.2.Action: NEB Academy and thematic groups

Together with partner InnovaWood the digiNEB partners decided to focus the Thematic Working Group for 'production and construction' toward the newly established NEB Academy launched by President von der Leyen.

Thematic Working Groups are being focused around individual topics of the digiNEB White Paper. This allows for regular and focused community engagement.

3.3.Future strategy: thematic events

We are currently planning three workshop series to reach out to the NEB target groups.

CAAD FUTURES

DigiNEB participates in the CAAD Futures event, organised this year at TU Delft from July 5-7. CAAD Futures (www.caadfutures.org) is a biannual international conference on Computer-Aided Architectural Design. CAAD Futures is profiled for advancing and documenting high-standard scientific research progress in the field. Its Community is richly diverse, aiming at broad interdisciplinary contributions as crucial in the built environment and widely supported by the potentials of computation.

CAAD Futures 2023 provides a great opportunity to organise two workshops to focus on the state of play regarding the use of digital innovation in design and architecture, and to identify gaps.

<https://www.caadfutures2023.nl/>

NEB Labs

Together with the University of Zagreb we are preparing a dual working late June linked to the Bauhaus Goes South NEB Lab.

NEB Lighthouses

In a similar fashion we prepare a dual workshop with the NEB Lighthouse NEBourhoods in Munich Neuperlach.

In short, we are addressing the communities of digital architects, NEB Labs and LEB lighthouses.

3.4.KPIs

The KPI associated with the TWGs is the number of policy briefs produced by TWGs. The target here is 4 for the full duration of the project.

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4. Strategy 3: Onboarding Early Adopters from the EU Regions

4.1.Planning: leveraging the Regional Innovation Model proposal developed with the European Committee of the Regions and the first digiNEB Early Adopters

The third strategy for onboarding Early Adopters focuses on the European Regions and leverages background work on a Regional Innovation Model completed as part of NEB High Level Round Table activities during 2022 together with the European Committee of the Regions, in a collaboration with Commissioner Ferreira's Cohesion Funds and INTERREG Europe, as well as best practice from pioneering and early successes of NEB regional initiatives.

4.1.1. Scaling the NEB Lab regional community co-creation model

At the meeting with President von der Leyen on the 28th of January 2022, Member of the NEB HLRT Michela Magas announced a joint proposal for scaling the results of NEB innovations from the ground up across the European regions, developed together with the European Committee of the Regions. This proposal has since been voted to be included as part of the official CoR statement at their 149th Plenary.

Press Release:

<https://cor.europa.eu/en/news/Pages/voucher-scheme-planned-to-support-cities-and-regions.aspx>

CoR Statement on NEB:

<https://cor.europa.eu/en/our-work/Pages/OpinionTimeline.aspx?opId=CDR-5640-2021>

First alignment of EU initiatives: On the 1st of March 2022 Michela Magas succeeded in gathering together members of Commissioner Ferreira's team working on the implementation of Cohesion Funds, the Rapporteur and representatives of the Committee of the Regions, and all of the representatives of Interreg Europe, including representatives of Région Hauts-de-France and DG Grow. The objective was to present the voucher scheme idea and see how existing funding mechanisms could be effectively connected in order to scale NEB innovations from the ground up. This fruitful meeting has been logged in extended minutes that highlight many important positive statements about joint collaboration.

Figure 9 summarises the core concept: an ecosystemic approach to EU funds that sees an unprecedented joining of forces to create a large-scale value network and a multiplier effect.

Following this meeting, Interreg Europe confirmed that they wish to launch calls that would fund the scaling of the most promising innovations. Representatives of the EIC declared that they were interested in capturing scaled innovations that correspond with the EIC's objectives. The colleagues implementing the Technical Assistance instrument from the Cohesion Funds have confirmed that the proposal is well aligned with the Cohesion activities.

The Committee of the Regions identified a legal precedent for funding this proposal with the WiFi4EU voucher scheme, which was launched in 2018 by President Juncker.

Onboarding of policy stakeholder groups:

- On the 4th of March 2022, Michela Magas presented this proposal to the Meeting of the Rapporteurs of European Parliament's Committee on Industry, Research and Energy (ITRE) and Culture and Education Committee (CULT) at the European Parliament.

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- Following Magas's keynote at the “Europe Cooperates” conference that launched the new Interreg programme, many regional stakeholders enquired about the possibility of running NEB activities in this way. Getting regional stakeholders on board was generally deemed to be a challenge, so this was considered by Interreg a very positive outcome.
- On the 21 April 2022, at the annual EU conference of the Culture and Creative Sector (ECIS22) introduced by the President and Commissioner Gabriel, after presentation of the proposal, multiple stakeholders enquired how they could help to make this proposal a reality.

Following the above interventions the joint proposal has evolved through ongoing EC meetings and has been represented in Parliament by Marcus Ros Sempere MEP.

The Regional Innovation Model for scaling from the ground up aligns with the Pact for Skills and EU Research & Innovation agenda by:

- Creating an unprecedented upskilling platform and multiplier for EU R&I
- Allowing for a flood of technology transfer from EU research to be tested and implemented by communities on the ground
- Connecting EU research with regional challenges and concerns
- Creating an ecosystemic approach to R&I for the built environment
- Implementing a transition to comprehensive inclusion for R&I participation
- Stimulating a fast, simultaneous and coordinated triple transition
- Making scaling of ideas to the level of excellence visible, desirable and achievable, creating a mission-driven culture throughout Europe.

Figure 9: Concept for a Regional Innovation Model scaling the results of NEB co-creation from the EU regions developed by Member of NEB HLRT Michela Magas in collaboration with the EU Committee of the Regions

4.1.2. The first digiNEB Early Adopters

The second component of the approach is designed to implement innovative processes on the ground that will create scalable results. It leverages the success story of the digiNEB Early Adopter Duved project (see <https://duvedmodellen.se/english/>), where a rural village of 1000 inhabitants in the North-West of Sweden has been turned into an engine for societal innovation achieving extraordinary results in just four years. The Duved Model was selected for the New European Bauhaus Forum panel session with Commissioner Ferreira in 2022 and was the first digiNEB Early Adopter community. The model was scaled as part of the NEB 'Visions in the North' initiative in Sweden for city development in Umeå as the 'Norrlands Model' and has been identified as best practice by the Council of Europe in view of deploying it across European regions. A regional cooperation has already begun with Norway and the Nordic Council of Ministers is supporting a network of 13 Border Committees.

Expected impacts of the scaling these models for regional ecosystems include:

- delivering pilot solutions of interconnected circular models based on concrete solutions in a rural area, that can be implemented and scaled in an urban context;
- curating and assembling expertise and practical implementation competencies from all domain segments to achieve synergies and efficiency;
- empowering leading talent to head teams of expertise to deliver solutions for prototypes based on citizens' needs and wishes;
- delivering prototype solutions based on new business and ownership models, based on deliberative processes and enhanced local democracy;
- identifying and developing environments that stimulate common understanding, co-creation, behavioural shifts and system change.
- delivering network solutions that will spread and communicate values as well as democracy and business models.

4.2.Action: Regional Innovation Model Handbook

In order to onboard regional ecosystems as digiNEB Early Adopters, the plan is to create a Regional Innovation Model Handbook that will assist regional communities in implementing innovative processes on the ground according to NEB principles, and scaling them through strategic alignment of EU mechanisms. The success of the Norrlands Model and digiNEB Early Adopter Duved project and its methodologies suggest ways in which such community-led and locally-focused innovation models could be replicated and scaled across a variety of different regional ecosystems in line with the New European Bauhaus objectives. In light of this ambition, **a draft Regional Innovation Model Handbook is presented in this document's Annexe.**

The Handbook provides a collection of strategies and activities for communities in regional ecosystems that takes into account the unique characteristics of each location. It is intended for anyone who is interested in societal development and sustainability, including policymakers, urban planners, architects, designers, and community members. The RIM Handbook provides a common starting point for place-based learning and community prototyping, and empowers local public servants, policy officers and community organisers to facilitate bottom-up action towards smarter societies and more sustainable local environments.

Building on several examples and lessons from the digiNEB Early Adopters, as well as significant additional research and related expertise in policy development and community innovation facilitation, the guidebook covers topics such as financial systems, democratic processes, working

with people from different fields of knowledge, and the importance of considering sustainability, energy, mobility, new production systems, regenerative materials and retrofit building in societal planning.

The purpose of the RIM Handbook is to provide both a conceptual and practical guide that aims to innovate societal development aided by digital technologies. The central concept is based on an updated version of the original Bauhaus circular model by Walter Gropius, and emphasises the need for a mutual vision at the local and regional community level. It aims to provide clear and practical guidance on how to work toward collaborative societal development from the ground up, and provides an updated approach to societal development that takes into account complexity and the need for a mutual vision within communities. The Handbook highlights the importance of connecting different fields that used to function separately, particularly within regional and city government structures, to encourage innovation with sustainable impact.

4.3. Future strategy: dissemination to the EU regions

Agreement has been reached with the European Committee of the Regions, the European Council, and the NEB EC team that the final version of the RIM Handbook will be disseminated by those bodies to European Regional Governments, EU regional initiatives and NEB communities. digiNEB will participate in the dissemination via its Early Adopters, EAG members and established community channels.

Engagement from dissemination will be focused towards the large multi-site NEB Festival that is being planned by NEB for spring 2024. In the lead up to this event engagement will be built, culminating with the onboarding of Early Adopters from multiple regions during the festival. Outcomes of the Early Adopter activities will be reported in D3.4.

4.4. KPIs

With the engagement of Early Adopters in the EU Regions, we plan to achieve several goals:

- At least 6 EU Regions engaged;
- At least 6 activities following the engagement;
- At least 100 regional Early Adopters added.

5. Strategy 4: Onboarding via social media dissemination and online platform

5.1. Planning

This strategy focuses on leveraging the project online platform, digineb.eu, as the main gateway to the Early Adopters community and the main way for them to get visibility, at pan-European level, among all the digiNEB.eu stakeholder groups. Moreover, this strategy implies the use of digiNEB.eu social media channels (i.e. LinkedIn, Twitter and Instagram) in a synergistic way with the website in order to better engage the audience, encourage participation and maximise the project's early adopter network's reach and impact.

As described in D5.1 – Plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication activities (DECP), a specific campaign is planned in the period M06-M18 as part of this strategy. The campaign is dedicated to Early Adopters onboarding and engagement and it leverages on multiple communication and engagement channels, such as direct **e-mails** to invite prospect members to join the Early Adopters' network, **events** with the onboarded Early Adopters, **press releases** and **success stories** about the Early Adopters' experience and impactful use of digital solutions, promotion via **social media** channels and Pay-per-click campaigns. In particular, social media and website are planned to support each other in early adopters engagement activities in various ways, including:

- **Cross-promotion and content sharing:** Social media channels will be used to promote Early Adopters' content which is published on the website, namely the application form, the pages displaying the onboarded Early Adopters, the digital solutions advocated by the adopters, their success stories. The websites and social media channels can share similar or complementary content to create a cohesive and consistent messaging, although in different forms. For example, the website will include blog posts or articles that provide more detailed information about the Early Adopters, while social media channels will share shorter updates or teasers that direct followers back to the website. This cross-promotion helps to increase traffic and engagement on both platforms, while maximising visibility for the Early Adopters.
- **Audience engagement:** Social media channels will be used to engage with the project's stakeholder groups and promote interaction with the Early Adopters. For example, the digiNEB.eu can post polls, quizzes, or surveys on social media to encourage followers to participate in the activities and share their experience.

5.2.Action: Early Adopter application form, webinars and success stories

The implementation of the strategy described above has gone through a series of actions, centred on the creation of meaningful content and entry points for the Early Adopters on the digiNEB.eu platform. These are detailed as follows:

Action 1: Set up & management of the Early Adopters Application Form. It is accessible at [this link](#) and has various entry points on the homepage and website main menu. The application form requires basic personal information, including the applicant's name, email address, and country of residence, as well as a brief statement explaining their interest in the New European Bauhaus and their experience with digital solutions supporting NEB. Once an application is submitted, the DigiNEB.eu team will review it and notify the applicants if they are accepted as an Early Adopter. The information provided in the application form will be used to feed the **Digital Toolkit** with new solutions and possibly create texts for the publication of **success stories**. Early Adopters will have access, whenever possible, to other digital solutions showcased on digiNEB.eu and will be able to provide feedback on their usability, functionality, and overall user experience. The following image display the promotion of the application form on the website and social media channels.

Early Adopters Application Form

Social media post promoting the application form

News piece promoting the application form

Banner in the home page with Call to Action

Figure 10 - Promotion of the Application form on the website and social media

The digiNEB.eu website management team will timely manage all requests received, making sure that all applicants receive a prompt answer and a fair and transparent evaluation process of their request. This will be done with the support of the Early Adopter Network Task Leader (ICF).

Action 2: Creation of web pages dedicated to Early Adopters. Once the application is successful, the applicant receives immediate visibility on the website where a dedicated page is created for each Early Adopter, as displayed in the image below. This is one of the central elements of the “win-win” strategy of the Early Adopter Network.

Cards displaying onboarded Early Adopters

Page dedicated to each Early Adopter

Figure 11 - Website pages dedicated to onboarded Early Adopters

Action 3: support to the organisation and promotion of events with Early Adopters. DigiNEB.eu has already organized two webinars in collaboration with early adopters such as representatives from **Bloxberg** (Sandra Vangadasalam) and **Duved** (Jan Åman) as part of its efforts to promote digital solutions for the New European Bauhaus. These webinars were duly promoted on the website and social media and brought together experts and stakeholders from different fields to discuss topics related to digital innovation, sustainability, and design. **Bloxberg**, a blockchain-based platform for academic research, was invited to DigiNEB.eu's webinar held on 14th February 2023 on the topic of digital identity and privacy. The webinar explored the potential of blockchain technology to provide secure and decentralized solutions for identity management and data protection. Participants discussed the benefits and challenges of using blockchain in the context of the New European Bauhaus and exchanged ideas on how to integrate this technology into future digital solutions. **Duved** was instead presented at the first digiNEB.eu webinar on 12th December 2022 and helped to highlight the importance of design thinking and user-centered design in empowering citizens and promoting social innovation in local communities.

Action 3: Set-up and management of a PPC campaign to recruit Early Adopters, pointing directly to the Online Webform. This will be implemented by using targeted ads that appear when potential users search for relevant keywords or browse relevant websites. For the success of the PPC campaign it will be important to identify the keywords and phrases that potential users are likely to search for when looking for digital solutions for the New European Bauhaus. This might include terms like "digital innovation," "sustainability solutions," "green architecture," and "smart buildings," among others. By carefully monitoring the PPC performance and adjusting the keywords, ads, and targeting as needed over time, it is possible to improve the effectiveness of the PPC and attract more Early Adopters.

Action 4: publication of digital solutions and success stories. digiNEB.eu is continuously publishing digital solutions in its toolkit and providing description of their use in the form of success stories displayed in the project's Observatory. The solutions proposed by the Early Adopters are included as well. As an example, see the **Democracy Tool** adopted in the context of **Duved** and the **Bloxberg solution** in the image below.

Figure 12 - Extract of Duved and Bloxberg's digital solutions and Duved's success story on the website

5.3.Future strategy

The contribution to Early Adopters coming from the digiNEB.eu website and the various social media channels will be continuously monitored, to make sure that the Early Adopter Network achieves the 100+ members that are targeted. According to that and to the feedback possibly gathered by the end-users, modifications to the web section dedicated to Early Adopters, as well as social media presence dedicated to them will be applied.

The key actions that will be implemented and monitored in the coming months to make sure the Early Adopters onboarding strategy on the website and social media is effective are listed as follows:

- **Use of the website as the main gateway to the Early Adopters community** and the main way for the Early Adopters to get visibility among all the digiNEB.eu stakeholder groups.
- **Cross-channel communication and promotion of Early Adopters and their results**, including all the communication assets and actions part of the Early Adopters Campaign (campaign #4), as described in deliverable D5.1.
- **Use of the project KERs as attraction tools for the Early Adopters**, namely:
 - the Thematic Working groups to which the Early Adopters can contribute,
 - the Digital Toolkit where digital solutions can be described,
 - the Observatory with success stories narrating the experience of Early Adopters, and the whole network of existing Early Adopters.
- **Creation of further digital material to promote and give visibility to Early Adopters**, such as dedicated social media posts with quotes from each adopter and dedicated video interviews.

5.4.KPIs

To tangibly monitor the impact of this specific digiNEB.eu strategy towards Early Adopters, the following measures will be tracked and their contribution to the achievement of the general project's KPIs will be assessed.

KPI Description	KPI at M24	Contribution of Strategy 4 actions to the KPI
Early Adopters	100	Number of Early Adopter applications received, number of accepted applications
Videos	24	Number of videos featuring Early Adopters' content
Social media content items published on socials (Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram)	192	Number of social media posts featuring Early Adopters' content
Marketing Campaigns	6	Number of marketing campaigns focused on Early Adopters

Table 2 Contribution of Strategy 4 to digiNEB.eu KPIs involving Early Adopters

6. Conclusions

This document has presented several strategies for the engagement of digiNEB Early Adopters and for the creation of an Early Adopter Network. Key ambitions have already been achieved, including:

- the creation of the digiNEB Early Adopter Network represented by a new hybrid community combining the digital and Smart Communities projects, NEB Lab and Lighthouse projects; and
- achieving Milestone MS4.1: First engagement and co-creation between digital R&I stakeholders and the NEB communities of practice, at the beginning of Month 6 of the project instead of Month 9 as planned in the DoA.

The impacts from the completed activities at the NEB@CERN community engagement event are far reaching and include key commitments by the newly established multidisciplinary community:

- commitment to ongoing engagement via regular in-person events organised by the NEB Lighthouses and Partners;
- establishment of Thematic Working Groups
- ongoing collaboration on a digiNEB community White Paper
- onboarding of further Early Adopters to the digiNEB community

Further strategies leverage the Thematic Working groups for further Early Adopter onboarding, background work in policy and success stories from NEB projects to engage the EU Regions, and the digiNEB online media to expand the Early Adopter Network.

7. References

digiNEB.eu - Deliverable D5.1 – Plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication activities (DECP)

digiNEB.eu – Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative has received funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) under Grant Agreement no. 101083743.

8. Annexe

Regional Innovation Model (RIM) Handbook (preliminary draft version)

Walter Gropius Bauhaus Circle diagram from 1922.

Remake/upcycle version of Walter Gropius Bauhaus Circle diagram from 1922 for New European Bauhaus Academy 2023 by Jan Åman and Adam Davies (13/03/2023)

ECOSYSTEMIC CIRCLE DIAGRAM

FROM BAUHAUS TO NEW EUROPEAN BAUHAUS

This ecosystemic circle is based on the Bauhaus circle, designed by Walter Gropius in 1922. Gropius designed it to structure the ground-breaking teachings at the Bauhaus School.

Walter Gropius' circle can therefore also be a way to understand the principles of the era for which it was created.

Today things have changed. On all levels. And this is what this circle and "handbook" is all about: new circumstances in a new era - and how that has an effect on how to structure societal development.

New circumstances require new structures - that will lead to a gradual shifts of systems. This in order to enable us to organise smarter societies, to make our local environments more sustainable, more

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resilient, and, not least, to enable us to work, engage and make decisions in a way that is in line with the conditions and possibilities of our time.

Returning to the circle of the Bauhaus in 1922, and up-dating/up-cycling it to our era is a way to visualise the needs, challenges and possibilities of today.

Setting the whole scope of things into one image is a way to understand the system of today - and thus to be able to act in ways that are more suitable to our time - simply to make way for the structural and systemic transformation that are the consequences of the Ecosystemic circle.

So, the circle can therefore be seen as a conceptual starting point for a new kind of “handbook” that aims at innovating societal development. It can be seen as a checklist, perhaps a common starting point to prototype and take action.

It is not an instruction to follow step-by-step. On the contrary.

The ecosystemic circle displays that it is time to include several new layers to consider in the societal planning of today. Things that one simply had not yet discovered in 1922, that were not even considered back then. Topics that also covers process and the way of organising everything from financial systems and how to be able to work with people from completely different fields of knowledge.

The circle is a tool to understand that we need to cover an enlarged scope today - following that the circle will include:

- The challenges and needs of today, globally as well as locally;
- Citizen’s engagement modes and updated governance models;
- Widened necessary set-up and specific areas to cover;
- The problems to solve;
- The ecosystemic content development;
- The prototyping action;

In 1922 the factory - and mass-production - had become the guiding principle - at least in the so-called Western world. The factory was the obvious icon for a society that turned towards rapid centralised living (urbanisation); centralised power structures (political and business); centralised production and distribution (mass-production); yes, even centralised cultural production (urban institutions). This opened for many great things. Not least accessibility for many to things that used to only for a few - and as a consequence of that, democracy.

It simply changed the world.

Walter Gropius and his contemporaries did not have to think about how to handle natural resources with care. Climate change was not on the agenda back then, the effect of industrial use of resources was not yet discovered. And, as we will see, many other layers have been added since then, as overall content, having an effect on basically everything.

An Ecosystemic circle diagram of 2023 is thus different from the circle diagram of 1922, in every sense.

For one, it is not linear.

The Circle of 2023 is not a timeline. (Even though one can follow the circle of 2023 and create a time from it, or the different steps you need to take.) It is a starting-point and a check-list. In a connected - ecosystemic - society the circle diagram is meant to be a tool to be used and layered on different parallel levels. All at once or one at a time. But keeping on principle: connectivity.

More than anything the 2023 circle diagram is meant to be a tool to use as a reference - in order to see how things could be connected and how to generate interaction. Thus the “handbook” is to be seen as a point of departure: to be developed by being put in use in different places, in different contexts and with different results and processes.

It is a check-list of fields to cover, not as separate entities, but together, in order to understand and come to terms with the complexity of today’s society. It is a tool to generate structures that could enable innovation with sustainable impact.

And just maybe, there might be a good chance that one can develop more engaged citizens, develop governance systems as well as new businesses - that could drive local societal structures forward.

The Ecosystemic circle diagram of 2023 is holistic, it is an overview that leads both to the centre and out from the centre, and back again.

It can never be applied in the same way in two different places, even if it would be in the same country or the same region. It is not about industrial scaling, to make the same all over again. It is about learning and developing systems, systems to be put in constant motion, developed and redeveloped, updated and upcycled.

This is why the Ecosystemic circle must be used and developed according to the circumstances in each place where it might be applied - with different conditions, different challenges and needs, different cultural backgrounds and, even more, driven by different personalities.

It is a “handbook” made to make future handbooks, through participatory processes.

But it does have one important aim: to accelerate solutions that can come to terms with the challenges that the planet is facing, urgently facing.

FROM INDUSTRIAL SILOS TO AN ECOSYSTEMIC CIRCLE

FROM CENTRALISED TO DECENTRALISED

FROM SPECIALISED TO CONNECTED

Industrial principle.

Ecosystemic

principle.

The two diagrams show a (simplified) image of the principles of the industrial era in comparison to that of today.

In an era of digital connectivity, of creating efficiency through matching different disconnected fields of interest together - an "ecosystemic" structure - a dialogue between different competences will be generated. This is the possibility and it is the challenge. We simply need to work and communicate in a different way from what we have been used to.

It is never easy to change.

The first image shows the industrial system - a system based on specification. The very idea of the factory was to produce a specific product of product line. And developed by those with knowledge in that specific field.

Within the industrial logic specific competence within a specific field are gathered, both in public and private sectors, in order to develop that given field. Housing is generated in one system. Infrastructure in another. Education yet another. Etc.

What is happening now is not that the specialised knowledge is out of the picture. On the contrary. It is more needed than ever. But today the specialised knowledge need to be in a much closer dialogue with other specialised fields of knowledge. So besides being competent in your own field you also need to be able to take information and ideas for other fields.

- How does this have an effect on the civil servant?

- How does this have an effect on business development?
- How does this have an effect on politicians?
- How does this have an effect on the local business?
- How does this have an effect on the system of “specialists”?
- How does this have an effect on citizens?
- How does this have an effect on each and everyone of us?
- How does this have an effect on communication?
- How does this affect language?

It is a demanding possibility.

Just to give an example:

Developing housing is no longer just about developing housing and building buildings. To develop future housing today one needs to consider many aspects other than just getting the building a building permit, get the documents through a bunch of consultants and then build.

it is no longer sufficient to stay there, to think it is enough to consider construction, assembly costs - and architectural profile. You need other, very different, expertise, to in parallel evaluate sustainability factors, affordability, new production and construction systems, where and how the production is set, how they can be produced by sustainable materials, with regenerative production processes, how they relate to energy consumption and future infrastructure solutions, what consequences it would have for the diversity of the social context, knowledged production, education, integration, culture, trade - and more.

It is a complex picture. Fun but complex.

The same goes for any area we would look into. Infrastructure is no longer just a question of rationally solving a traffic flow. It is also a question of energy, sustainability, of the local. As opposed to the regional, of the world post fossil fuels, of how to make a city or village centre vibrating with life and where the public spaces are actually used and not just there to look at - as well as question of security for pedestrians, bicyclists, of smart local transport systems - as well as of local production.

It is a complex picture. Fun but complex.

Fields that used to function in themselves, for themselves, are, by necessity, being connected. Out of necessity. Urgent necessity. We are on all levels leaving silos to enter an ecosystemic development process. we are forced to do so.

This means that each and everyone - private as well as public - need to adjust to a new situation that comes out of a technological shift. The consequences of digitalisation have an effect on everything: how we live, work, act, organise - and communicate.

It is not enough to add yet another specialised field or segment. It is not enough to add a new department, of say, sustainability or governance. The problem to solve is how specialised knowledge in one field can be implemented and integrated into other fields.

This means that, for instance, a building permit in a city planning department needs to be considered from a wider range of contents and values. The architecture criteria and how the house blends into the city's historical values, is added by a number of other values, that include a number of additional information (as stated above).

You will soon see what consequences that will have.

This generates what can be called an “ecosystemic possibility” – or rather necessity – on societal development. Something that would have an effect on everything in the development structure:

Process. Structure. Dialogue. Engagement models. Production. Life.

This opens up for many things, as you will see. It has an incredible potential. But for many reasons (production systems as well as the need for dialogue) the shift from centralised to decentralised and ecosystemic open up for a focus on local systems, structures of a smaller scale.

To put it simple: the local is the future.

And the local can be implemented, in different ways according to context, to other local contexts – and upwards, from neighbourhoods to cities, to regions, to nations. From the decentralised to the centre – i.e. flipped positions. And, if this is the future of development structures, it brings us closer to the people, to the citizens, and to the life that is possible to live in our communities.

CHALLENGES AND NEEDS

LOCAL AND GLOBAL

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The perhaps the most important difference from the Bauhaus diagram of 1922 is this outer circle: Challenges and needs, and to consider them both from a global as well as local perspective. See these words as delicately interconnected.

The challenges and needs can be written in two short words: Climate and Democracy.

This is a major change.

One that requires a bit of background.

CLIMATE

In the early days of the industrial era there were only possibilities. New modes of production were invented. Instead of handicraft goods, things were mass-produced through the factories' production lines – which reduced costs and made products accessible for a mass-audience.

There was simply no need to be aware of the fact that resources were exploited. The very idea did not exist (in a broader meaning). Nor that the way things were produced could damage the environment and the global climate.

The idea of the circle diagram is to show that climate – by being a major initial circle – is a topic that should be added as an integrated part into each and every segment of each and every layer and part of the circle, not as an add-on. The UN Sustainable Development Goals, those that were formulated during the World's Fair in Milan 2015, make up a good guide to follow.

And one should keep in mind, things are even more urgent in 2023 than in 2015.

One could say that climate/sustainability is the very future in every sense. We need to achieve a more sustainable way of organising our society – in order for the planet to survive. But it is also the future of innovation and thus the future of business. We'll get back to that.

This means that the idea of developing local societal processes based on sustainability can and should be part of all processes: the citizen's model, the governance system, the set up of segments, the problems to solve, the ecosystemic structure, as well as the action and doing.

Today the idea of a ZERO WASTE society is no longer a utopia. On the contrary. During the past ten years there have been plenty of examples developed, both within food systems, regenerative materials, production/ construction of design and architecture as well as of infrastructure solutions, storage, circular economies and much more.

The technological development is rapid. Today there are AI systems that can put each local community in dialogue with other initiatives, so you will never have to start at a blank paper.

With chefs like Douglas McMaster the idea of ZERO WASTE has been communicated and thus accepted. We are not there yet. But it could be something that can belong in every kitchen, public and private. The same goes for many other areas. What is needed now is to systematically implement knowledge that already exists and put it in motion. The solutions exist. The Ecosystemic circle could be a tool to get started.

Because the thing is, the local context is the one thing that has been missing. There are plenty of new companies with new smart solutions. There are more every day. But they need a context to be developed together.

By starting a process in a local context – such as a neighbourhood or a village – will add a new value: the possibility of getting different technological solutions, different new companies to be further developed side-by-side – and thus by being put in dialogue between each other. This means the

future of business will be developed on site, in neighbourhoods, in dialogue with entrepreneurs, with academic specialists, and together with the users, i.e. the citizens.

Because the fact is that the digital era – connecting and ecosystemic – is ideal for developing the solutions that are needed. It makes way for innovations and new businesses – and business models – that will be the future and that will create both the future business and the sustainable societies.

This sets the smaller local system in a central position. It is no longer the urban centre that will lead the way. The centre will follow and have solutions implemented from smaller communities, neighbourhoods and/or villages.

Again, flipped positions. A whole new way of organising our societal development.

DEMOCRACY

One of the most important achievements of industrialisation was modern democracy. The new production system – i.e. the factory – changed the social and economical reality and allowed for the many to have what before only was for the few. Modern democracy was founded, which was a revolution.

In 2023 the world is again very different. Technological development has given us a new modus operandi, where we all are used to being able to express our opinions and feelings directly, through our smart-phones and computers.

It is not an easy transformation. According to the 2022 Democracy index, published by The Economist, only 8% of the global population live in what is called full democracies, whereas 36,9% live in authoritarian regimes. With recent year's development in full democracies the threat there is an obvious need to find ways to not only strengthen the democracy but to find new ways of how to engage and involve the citizens in their own future – and thus ways of how to address and attract people to take part in societal development.

This brings us back to the local scale.

On a local local, smaller scale, there is a greater potential to involve the citizens to be part of a dialogue and to engage in their own neighbourhood's future. There is a better chance to develop an ecosystemic structure on the local scale – to be part of developing and defining the future rather than just voting for the selected fews to represent them.

This can be given different names, such as "ecosystemic democracy" or "deliberative democracy" and in fact the two terms point out specific action points.

One – ecosystemic – that the citizens actually become more involved in the entire process.

The other – deliberative – that this requires a dialogue between the different partners in the structure.

We'll examine both later in this document. And of course, by focusing on the local scale there is a possibility of generating a reversed process – of starting at the local scale and there generate an interplay between citizens, public and private partners – and then, gradually, move upwards in the political structure.

At the same time this opens for yet another possibility: language.

The language and forms of dialogue and information need to be accessible and engaging. Through the local democratic models the language and the forms of dialogue and interplay a new democratic vocabulary could be developed, in tune with our times. This might be the most important of all factors to secure and up-cycle the future of democracy.

LOCAL DEMOCRACY MODELS

GOVERNANCE MODELS

Time to move into the parts that are closer to that of a "handbook".

As follows of the above, a smaller, local and ecosystemic structure, have an opportunity to develop a model where the citizens are directly involved in the development the vision of their local community.

Connectivity has always been a key to smaller local communities. The traditional neighbourhood – or the village – is based on local sharing. With digital tools this has a possibility to be reactivated in a high-tech era.

So, focus on the local.

The local have a possibility strengthen democracy. As well as to come to terms with climate issues. Global challenges meet local needs.

From the local, try to generate an interplay between the three main partners: the citizens, the public sphere and business.

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The aim is to get a closer relationship between the citizen's wishes, local knowledge and engagement with the public sector's mission to handle common issues – as well as with the business' possibility to finance, invest and execute.

Just as everything else there has in most cases been too much of a split between these different groups of interest. It is not easy to interact and to be engaged in common issues. That is why you need both a language and a method that works. We need to innovate the models of interplay and connections between the three. The possibilities of an ecosystemic interplay is a bit different from that of the traditional definition of top-down representative democracy – as well as that of a bottom-up democracy. And by the way, both of those had the very best intentions. It is just that times they are a-changing. And this leaves us with a possibility.

The Ecosystemic (or deliberative) structure is about adapting the current system so that it fits a digitalised, connected society. The structure and players within a system remain – the shift is rather how each and everyone are perceiving and redefining their own function and role. They turn from their previous positions – to all be "enablers" for each other and the totality of the structure in order to take in the full scope of the Ecosystemic Circle.

This may sound as an easy thing to achieve. But it is a rather big cultural and behavioural shift. For each and everyone in the system.

This would require that the citizens are not just responding to decisions made elsewhere – but given a responsibility. Both in an initial stage and all along the process.

The civil servants become enablers, enablers with kept responsibilities, but now based on inclusion – i.e. to include the partners and expertise needed, so that solutions may have the possibility to be realised. And through this the goal may be reached – to make the local society sustainable, resilient and lively. Expertise is needed, but set in motion and in parallel with other expertise.

The role of business and investment is different as well, as will be showed in the next circle.

There are many possible solutions to how this new role for democracy and governance may be developed – all according to the current systems and possibilities in each and every region and community. But they need to happen and they need to be put in writing not to stay as ever so promising words.

In the village of Duved, the CEO of the municipal real estate company, owned to 100% by the tax-payers, Mrs Helen Olausson, launched a model that proved to be successful in that local context.

By – together with private investors and with the Village Association – forming a mutual development company and setting very clear rules for it, she managed to generate a structure that is fulfilling these requirements. One that is truly ecosystemic, with the following ownership model:

- The public sector have, through the real estate company, 25% of the shares in the new development company, but are also given the right to select the CEO and the chairman of the Board of directors.
- The Village association have 6,8% the shares of the company, but are also given a "golden share", i.e. a share that give the citizens the final vote in case of conflict within the Board of directors.
- The private companies, the business side, have in total 68% of the shares – but have agreed to these new circumstances, and thus agreed to be part of the dialogue with the citizens and the public sector.

Alas, a new business model was initiated. One that combines the citizen's engagement and responsibility, the public sector's responsibility for the tax-payers and long-term goals with financial security to actually be able to pull off necessary investment.

But this is just one way of doing it. What it created by being initiated by the municipal real estate company was the possibility of being both inside and outside of the civil system of the municipality. Keep that in mind. It is crucial.

But in whatever way one move this forward to an Ecosystemic structure, get it in writing.

This connected way of structuring societal development is a big shift. It is about adapting to a new world. The civil society need to set up goals that are long-term and visionary, visions that can make a difference. Sustainability goals. Innovation goals. Engagement goals. It would guarantee a system that does not try to fix things from the centre, but that actually try to decentralise the system itself: a society where the societal development is looked upon with holistic approach, with the citizens in the centre.

To make things happen, it is needed to involve the citizens from an initial phase.

If the citizens are not part of a development plan from the beginning the old system will remain. This is nothing new. All through history this is a classical battle. In Florence, in 1293, Giannozzo della Bella challenged the ruling families by introducing a system where the different guilds in the city were given a much larger say in the development of the city. The representatives of the guilds were replaced every second month.

So, find a local, citizen-driven organisation, a non-for profit. Or create one. Partnership with public sector and private sector. Make a mutual structure with set goals, with a vision, where everybody agree on the end goal. Then it is possible for entities to handle the process, and to match all the partners that are needed. As you will see this is just a ground work to set the possibilities that are the consequences of today's society, where academic structure no longer are confined to the "house" in the city, where the need to match finance and innovation and research are brought in dialogue with the actual doing. This is what the Ecosystemic Circle is all about.

FINANCIAL MODELS

BUSINESS MODELS

The local ecosystemic circle could be seen as a wheel, in the sense that it is a circle to put different entities in connection to each other and – in motion, in getting them to generate greater efficiency, cut costs, and get more out of each transaction and/or product. By connecting dots the circle makes every dot larger than the dot itself.

Does it sound strange? It is not. It is a pretty normal principles within digital-/tech-systems. Tech is structured to disrupt already existing business sectors, to cut costs, make them smarter and more – by connecting the dots save money and make new business.

That is why the ecosystemic circle indicate a transfer from silos to connectivity. This could, in fact, be seen as a blockchain IRL. The centre is no longer the centre. The action (and the business) is no longer coming from the centre, but from a decentralised connectivity. Instead of dividing decisions and money into different categories and systems it suggest the opposite. It starts from the larger picture, the whole circle and all the content that goes into it – and thus open for a completely different ballgame.

This has a huge impact on the system of financing and investing, in fact, the entire world of business.

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In an old industrial system both money and decisions are divided. Municipal, regional and national entities have different budgets, different ways of taking decisions. By matching the players, by creating the ecosystem, things will instead be more efficient. If citizens, investors and the civil system talk instead of protecting their positions – a lot of money will be saved. This will also generate more satisfied citizens since there will be a better chance that things will actually be done and effectuated. Action speak louder than words.

Dialogue fosters dialogue. So if knowledge is shared there there will probably be more knowledge added, from partners that suggest that someone else is needed. And thus create a possibility for new business. Or new culture. The core of the matter is to start the process – that everyone have to talk, listen and learn from each other.

Decentralisation means that even large companies will have to remodel themselves in order to develop local business models with system scaling rather than product scaling. Mass production is a phenomena of the past, but to keep costs down there will be other necessary ways to scale. Simply because they will need to, both in order to make a business and to be sustainable.

As you will see in the coming, there are many factors that generate future local businesses. Moving from wear and tear to a circular system there will – on a larger scale – need to be ways to collect what is no longer used. There will need to be ways of how to regenerate the material, to produce new things, and up-cycle what was used. This goes from everything from food to clothes, from furniture to housing, from plastic to wood, from steel to nature. And do not forget – it goes from supply-chains to production, from process development to democratic models.

The Ecosystemic Circle of 2023 suggest a gradual shift from short-term to long-term models, both for investments and for business. The early tech-phase idea, of investing in many start-ups, with the goal to have one or two making it, is just not sustainable. That is a rest from the wear and tear economy, from the assembly line. The technological transformation to a digital economy demands the opposite. But what have been lacking is a local context, to bring the innovation out to reality, where the innovations can test and develop by interacting with others – and with the user, the citizens.

The ecosystemic financial system is learning from the local process. It needs to take care of financial resources, make them efficient and make them sustainable. Investments – and the products coming out of investments – has a long term goal.

Combine forces. Get everyone to work together. This creates power to execution and to actually get things done.

Start in small scale. Prototype for learning and to reach innovation goals. Then move on the bigger projects.

Business models both in larger cities and in local communities are in a much greater sense being based on partnership use and multi-use. The idea of one function only has been challenged for a long time now. Basically everything is about making the most of what you have. A kitchen can be used for public food in the morning and for a restaurant in the evening. A square in the city can be used for leisure and at the same time for temporary markets and to grow food.

This is moving the financial system out into the local doing, the action. It is to create a context for investment. A next generation of investments funds will be smaller, and local, and driven by AI, to learn from others, and never start on a blank canvas. This is to move the innovation out from the innovation silos. And into an ecosystem in real life.

THE SET-UP

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A new era require a new set-up of which areas to cover and to instigate a real ecosystem. See it as a possible game plan. If you set things up in the right way, the wheel just might begin to turn, and people might just gradually get more and more accustomed to an ecosystemic reality, where they do not at first hand protect their position but exchange content, share experiences – and synergy can begin.

BE CO-CREATIVE

As written above the key to all development and innovation within societal development of today is that the era of silos is over, to be replaced by an interactive ecosystemic structure.

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With this structure follows that knowledge and decisions are decentralised by bringing in others into each to handle the complexity of today's society and the challenges that we are facing.

For some this may create confusion – about what co-creation is all about. By demanding that people from the same field of knowledge to develop things together it may even be creating insufficiency. But the real value is when it is applied in expertise from other fields than your own.

So – be even sharper and more precise within your own field. Don't make things complicated. But bring in expertise from other fields and always, always ask yourself: how can what I am about to do be done in a way that would be smarter and lead to a more sustainable world and contribute to the future of the local community.

UNDERSTAND THE TECHNOLOGY SHIFT

It may seem obvious. But it is more complicated that you may think. The technological shift towards a digitalised world is not about technology. It is about changed behaviour. Behaviour that can be applied to driving the local community in a smarter and more sustainable way.

There are several things to be learned from this. One is that a new IT-department is the wrong way to go. Bring the idea of IT and tech into all other sectors, like a new part of the language or alphabet that they use. It is almost like a new profession: people that are not just experts in selling IT-solutions, but rather advising on the consequences of digitalisation.

Tech connects and can make systems, ecosystems, more efficient. There are plenty of solutions for this. Use what you find and try it in smaller scale, for instance on food systems or local construction systems or infrastructure. Test and try. Connect different players. You will most probably see how the different players become more prosperous. Perhaps will their contribution to one local system be implemented elsewhere. Within a new context.

Check the very quick development of things. AI got a big breakthrough during the past months. It is a tool, only a tool, to make comparative studies very quickly. It makes it possible to find out what others have already innovated, things that may help you and your specific circumstances in your local context.

The same goes for digital twins. The phenomena used to be a way for consultancy firms to charge more money. Now they are much smarter, less expensive and can be put in use inside and not outside the organisation.

So, bring the tech-knowledge inside your own organisation, as an integrated part of everything, and make it into a tool to create an ecosystem with the others you need to play with.

SEE EVERYTHING AS A LIFE-CYCLE

This is old knowledge becoming new. Before the era of factories and industrial production it was common knowledge. Things had a life-cycle. They were used and re-used. They were transformed. A table could turn into a stool. Or something else.

In the 1990's the British chef Fergus Henderson introduced "Nose to Tail Cooking", reintroducing the idea to use the whole animal for cooking, not just the fillet of beef and ground meet, as the industrial principle suggested.

It turned out to be one of the most important contributions to innovate the food systems in ages. In a subtle way it revolutionised the the whole idea of food production. By returning to an old – and almost forgotten – knowledge, a cooking from the age of grandma, Fergus Henderson reintroduced flavours and a way of thinking that felt contemporary. And without having that intention Fergus Henderson – who is trained as an architect – created a starting point of a new idea of creative production, that has exploded in the later years. To use given resources to the full. And by that gaining something that was lost. Not least the beauty of taste.

It is only with industrialism that the Western world got accustomed to the idea of wear and tear – that became a way of living, based on consumption. Consumption of resources. A way of living that produces waste and that we now know is not sustainable.

A new generation of chefs, designers and architects already have just about all the knowledge, the ingenuity, and the rethinking that is needed. And through and with them comes a whole new generation of companies that have and develop the solutions that are needed. So, you will not have to work in the dark or from a white sheet of paper.

The thing is, that this basically changes all everything as we know it. In the cities there will not jut be places to buy stuff, produced elsewhere. There will be hubs with companies that take care of and recycle and up-cycle products that are ready to take the next generation of itself.

There will be local production units, mobile factories or assembly-places. And again, this means that part of the production and part of the retail of things will be local. This means that also for the larger players are developing new production-, distribution- and business models. All perfect for and needing a participatory dialogue in a community based context.

When you look at the next circle, inside of this, you will find a selection of problems to solve. Apply the lifecycle performers on each and every segment. It will be a key to develop solutions for the future. Also link it to financial models, accelerators and/or incubators. What this heading bring is a whole new business and innovation model to the local community.

It will be possible to follow some examples through the digiNEB, and there are many other channels as well where you can find smart solutions for a sustainable future based on new business linked to culture. The systems for this are being quickly developed. AI and other tools are getting better and better. Try to find different sources where you keep yourself updated to current developments.

AN INCLUSIVE AND TENTATIVE DEVELOPMENT PROCESS IS KEY

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This might be both the toughest and the most important factor to establish to reach a sustainable, resilient and innovative societal development. If this is not done properly from the start you will have a hard time going back and fix it. It might even be impossible. So think things through from the beginning. There are some tough decisions to take.

A key factor here is how you set budget and money. In most cases, the way you apply for money, both from public sources and within companies, is to secure as much capital as possible from the very beginning. The way success is evaluated is usually to look upon how much money you are able to gather before you begin.

Well, good luck!

This would mean that you need to formulate the entire process from the beginning, foresee coming steps and, from the start, know what the end result will be.

Don't do it. It is thinking and acting like an old-time factory line. Linear in a way that linear was never intended to be. It just doesn't work. Not anymore.

The world is too complex today. And that is why most projects and processes that claim to develop innovation simply are not innovative. It is easier to cover the right words and phrasing – claiming innovation – than actually getting the action to innovation IRL. Innovation is to search for that which is not known and is yet to be developed – before you start looking for it. Unfortunately the conditions for public money are structured – for very good reasons, to avoid corruption – in a way that is extremely demanding.

Unfortunately creating problems on the other side: only larger firms can hire people with a profession only to make applications. The big consultancies feast.

This is a problem that needs to be tackled.

It is an important structural problem to handle – with the consequence that the entire system needs to update itself, which should be a pilot in itself:

- How you apply for money.
- How to evaluate processes.
- How money is gathered.
- How to act, do and prototype.

That is why the ecosystemic circle is important. It may be a tool to check and structure your work.

Ideally you should start with a process where the first step is to gather the players – i.e. the ecosystem, from citizens to investors over to the political system – and together formulate the why, the what and the how. It might take a few workshops. But this is not expensive. On the contrary. The little money you spend here will save you money all along the coming process. And, to be honest,

this is the only money you need to start with. But you need to structure the process so that you can develop the financial process along the way.

Divide the initial ideas into different categories (take a look at the content development circle and you'll find a possible, initial checklist), but make sure you also look at these things with the following in mind:

- What is possible to set quickly, as temporary injections, to start telling the story and to get people engaged into what you, together with them and other players, of which many are still unknown. What these injections are will be the result when you strategically analyse the results of participatory workshops. Be sure to secure partners and funding for this part. Because it is important.
- The injections is a start to tell a story and that is what the local context that you work with could tell and that this should have an impact on everything that you do, from larger constructions, to retail and events planning.

If you, as you should, always bring in expertise from different fields in every single thing that you want to make happen, it is an inclusive process where partners come in all along the way. But it is also a constantly reversed process. Where the results for the expertise working together in co-creation, is constantly brought back to the community and to the citizens.

The idea of an inclusive process is to deliver a sustainable process – that can give long term results and where the first steps are connected to the last. This means that whatever occurs as things happen – it could be collaborations with academia, with schools, with constructions companies etc – all should be integrated into the same development structure, the same ecosystemic structure, and thus generate synergies, which means innovation, and, at the same time develop a community.

MAKE SURE YOU UPDATE THE DEMOCRATIC MODEL

Again, it's no rocket-science. It really isn't. It is all a matter of where to start.

And, yet again, it is crucial that you do this

The future is local and the future is to move from top-down and linear to instead be based on a connective interplay between the different players that can make a change, together. That includes the citizens as part of the process from the start.

First of all, define the scale you are working with. It should be small enough to be called local, i.e. a neighbourhood, a defined part of a city – or a village. Define which parts of the Ecosystemic Circle that you are targeting.

In a neighbourhood or a village there are usually and naturally connections between the citizens. They take their kids to school and to different activities together. They meet at the local pub or café. They go to the same supermarket. They share a common everyday life. This makes them share

thoughts of common interest. How buses or other public transportation works. The opening hours of the café. Security for their kids. What to do when you are retired. How to attract more newcomers. How to handle those that move in. The possibility for their kids to have an education. The life-cycle that follows. You get it – they share an interest in their local community. They might talk about that. Or not. But they share it

So, to develop a democratic model that is more updated to our time, the local community is the perfect starting point. Why now and not before? As written earlier because the industrial system had as a core principle the idea of centralisation. The post-industrial society is, through the production and technological developments, much based on decentralisation. The shift that is well underway and that is being developed rapidly will bring us back to a connected local starting-point.

Most things needed for an updated democratic model are already in place in the local community.

What it needs is a rush and a push – and a strategy.

In many places people have not been accustomed to actually take part in the societal development of their own local neighbourhood. It seems to be part of the modern life. They might have very clear opinions of what others decide, but are not used to be part in the development of their own neighbourhood, neither, of course, in running it, or, even more, own it. This is today's big challenge and the big opportunity. And it is something that needs careful planning, lots of discussions, dialogue and collaborative processes.

There are, again, many ways on how to bring this to action. You'll see further in the coming chapters. But the core principle is to find a platform where the dialogue can begin, where it is not run by neither the political or the public structure, not by the investors either, but together. To keep an integrity in the process there are many possible ways to create this initial interplay between the three major components of societal development: the citizens, the political/public sector and the investment and business.

CREATE A COMMUNITY

For the updated – Ecosystemic – democratic model to last and be sustainable, you need to create a community. That is, a structure that makes it natural for people to meet, to talk, to meet civil servants – and vice versa. To meet others who also want to do and make action. Others that want to join forces – and through that have a greater strength to actually execute and do. When asking for permits, when wanting to build or start a business it is easy to say no to a lonely player. But it is far more difficult if many (and differentiated) forces have come together in some kind of mutual vision. Money speaks. Political power speaks. A strong alliance between the citizens speak. What about when you get these three to act together?

Well, the thing is to get them there. We'll come to that, but first, a remark.

Communities are sometimes perceived as the equivalent to traditional bottom-up citizensdriven initiatives. There is nothing wrong with them, but the Ecosystemic idea is based on connections between different players – from citizens to specialist, from finance to political system, from creatives and back to citizens. So, with this, things are a bit more complex. Remember, if the industrial model was based on centralisation and specialisation the model that is about to take place

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now is about decentralisation and connectivity. And that the right place to get it going is the local, i.e. the not so large social context.

This is a new kind of community. Maybe even a new definition of a community, an "ecosystemic community". The common principle is not only the common but, and even more so, the difference. It is community where the different partners are different but have a common goal, or an idea of a common goal. The different players of the community are responsible to talk to the others, to be in a dialogue with partners that are not like yourself. That is a different kind of responsibility. A community based on common interests but also on different skills and roles to play in the interactive game. The short-term business is not leading, the politicians are not leading, the bottom-up is not leading. Instead they are dependent on each other.

That, as we have seen, and will see, are relationships to be sealed by being put in writing. It has to be given a legal structure and the reason for this is, again, a simple one: otherwise it will be too easy to fall back into old patterns.

Such a community need to, somehow, formulate a mutual vision, a mutual narrative, a mutual understanding. Something that is very different from a consultancy slogan. It does not have to be fancy. It is a matter of knowing where you're heading, long-term.

The most important thing is to start a position for the community where you have an integrity but are in dialogue with the entire system, inside but outside. The starting point could be a company owned by the municipality, i.e. the tax payers. Companies that have a double mission: to function as an independent company and make a reasonable profit, but also to serve the needs of the many. But there are several other options, all according to context, to habits, rules and regulations where this is to be done.

The second most important thing is to have a real mission of doing, of action, of prototyping and get things done. The problem with most systems, be they public or private, is the same (and it grows with size), that they are usually good in using fancy words and having meetings and writing papers, but not so good at action.

Why? Because it is difficult for them. They have one foot, if not two feet, in business models that are not yet ecosystemic. But since they will be heading in the ecosystemic direction it is mainly a matter of time until they get there. So they need you. They need to be part of the change.

A community need a common place, a venue, a meeting spot, both a physical and a digital one. A couple of tools are described under the headline below. Ideally the physical space should embed the feeling of, and be a local icon for, the vision of the ecosystemic development and its goals.

And it should from the very beginning be a organised and structured so that it goes beyond meeting. It should embed the local incubator, drive forward to local funds for generating new local jobs and initiatives, things that drive a local economy further and one that enhances the ideas of a local, ecosystemic economy. And remember that this is where large part of the future business will happen.

A community need a purpose and it needs models that generate longterm engagement. Again, this is where the ecosystemic structure hits in, to get the wheels in motion, to make people and structures to interact and find ways of how to exchange information and to get players that are used to negotiate from opposite positions to sit on the same side of the table and come with mutual visions.

MAKE SURE TO SET THE SITE

To live, work or invest somewhere, in a neighbourhood, is not the same thing as fully understanding the structure of the neighbourhood. Our ways of understanding is based on our specific interests.

The citizens, the people that actually live in a place, have the that everyday knowledge of the place, of where certain things are on the supermarket shelves, when the bus leaves, what works and what is lacking, they know if a specific piece of land is very important for common activities. And so on.

The civil servant at the planning office may have an overview of the neighbourhood, for completely evident reasons, but based on a way of viewing that is now about to take in many other points of view. Where those of the citizens should be a very important tool to understand things better, as an initial input, not later when things are set.

But also, as mentioned earlier, all these other things that are now on the global agenda: sustainability, energy, mobility, new productions systems, regenerative materials and retrofit building.

The investors need to make a good investments. In the old days it was easier to just build a building or open a business, but as the world is getting more complex you need to understand the others wishes, needs and ideas. So you get it right from the beginning. Short-term is out. Long-term is in. That is way to save money and time, and to make money. But in a slightly new way.

It is important to get these different players to work – and play – together, as well as separately. To start the process. To get the generating of a mission in action.

And you need some tools.

A very facts-on tool, analog and and simple and that is tested and proven efficient is the following:

- invest in a large areal photograph printed on a large canvas (like the ones that are put on facades for commercial messages). Roll it on a floor. A print like this is strong enough to walk on (but be sure to take your shoes off before entering). It strong enough to put imaginary houses or other new stuff on (could be in wood or in any material, it is like a very big monopoly game. The material is strong enough to use and reuse over and over again.
- Print it in a scale so that the photograph is large enough to really walk on and to get the sensation from walking on your own city or neighbourhood, and so that you can play on, like a computer game IRL. Which means, so that you both get an overview and where it is large enough to really see gaps in the city, to see the infrastructure, the timeline in which the city was built, the connections, the empty spaces. Simply in a way makes you want to work with it, and start playing with it.
- If you do this right everyone who lives in och works with what is on the photograph will immediately see things both with a surprised perspective that open ones eyes and make you smile – and, after awhile, walking on it, seeing those personal connections, to where you live, where others live, what you have done in one place, where you went swimming, kissing or shopping. Wether you are a school kid or a professional city planner you will most probably have the same kind of initial sensation and experience.
- For a photograph of that size you need to have a big room, ideally more than 250 square meters. The sensation is greater if it is big and the urge to play and work on it too. A larger room also generates a feeling of creative possibilities.

- The workshops groups should consist of people of different backgrounds, different age groups, different roles within the ecosystem. To mix established players with students and to mix locals with professionals usually triggers results.
- You can structure the process in many different ways, at time (necessary) to invite everyone, all groups of interest, sometimes to more specific questions that need to be discussed.
- Ideally you should also have separate spaces for group discussions after workshops on the aerial photograph. It could be as large as possible, so that the people working there get a feeling of flying over their own neighbourhood, to establish a feeling of possibilities.
- It would require an entire handbook to describe the way to run a workshop. But some key advise:
 - Be very precise in what questions you want answered.
 - Be very well prepared so that you have done research beforehand (this will never ever be a problem in the sense that you will know the answers beforehand, because you will not – the workshop groups will be independent anyway, but your job is to get them energised and precise.
 - ask for communicative answers, so that you are not stuck with words and phrases.

Once you start getting answers, take notes and, document, not for the sake of the document, but for the sake of starting to act upon. From the documentation you can start completing both a storyline, a time-line and a list of preferred things, on how to proceed. And then check if you got the message.

Once this is in order, there are several things to think about:

- analyse and, again, decide what is possible to start with without too much of a hassle and too much of a budget, so that you get going and get people with you to see that things were not just words but action; it might be temporary projects, but define them in a way so that they really are a starting point of a bigger picture and story.
- define a sequence of actions, from small to big, and communicate them with everyone involved – if you get the citizens in it is a bigger chance you'll also convince the civil servants.
- Get a digital version for smartphone use going, where you can have the aerial photograph and data on it, so that it becomes both informative and interactive. There are pilots of tools like this being soon available

BEGIN WITH EDUCATION AND LOCAL KNOWLEDGE SYSTEMS

Everything in this "handbook" is meant to increase the understand the consequences of the transformation to an ecosystemic world, i.e. a connected world where the need for interaction between different partners is essential. And with this follows that each and everything in a societal systems should be regarded as exactly that. It may seem silly to repeat this – but it is a big shift.

The question here is what effect this has on both the local education system (schools) as well as with academic research and teaching. A lot.

Let us start with the school. The school has always been central for the local community. That is where the kids are, of course, but the kids have parents and the kids have teachers. It is a pretty large

part of the societal context. So, look upon your school's possibility in this way if you don't do so already:

Involve the kids in the societal discussion. Kids are amazing innovators because they have ideas that are not stuck in how things are usually done. They are not yet in the system and have their eyes and imagination open – which means that their ideas can be, and usually are, a great way to discover new possibilities, so put them on the aerial photograph and you'll be sure to get food for thought.

Involve the teachers and the parents once you have the kids, simply, because then you have a backbone of the entire local community, and – as a consequence – you will have a crossgenerational dialogue.

Use the school to start the local ecosystemic food system (see the next chapter). Kids have an influence of their parents and kids are easy to learn. Put food as part of the learning process, try to grow vegetables within the school or close to it. Invite chefs and create program for learning to cook and ask the children to learn their parents as well. (This idea is proven to be successful in Peru, in a beautiful project launched by the chef Gaston Acurio and the government.) Push for zero waste in the school and it will spread further into the community.

Use the school's facilities for multi-use. If kids are there in daytime other activities can be taking place nighttime. Why not cooking-classes to widen the ideas that kids are already involve in.

The kitchen in a school is usually big and professionally equipped – use it for multipurpose, maybe for recycled food to be served elsewhere and why not at restaurants or to be sold at local supermarket, The same goes for classrooms. They are very suitable for meetings and activities of all sorts.

Invite the elderly to be part of the process of an ecosystemic school. This is also a proven method in different places around the globe (it used to be the normal way of living). The elderly could be in charge of the school's garden, and of off-hours activities. It creates bonds in-between generations.

Knowledge systems and the ecosystemic:

The transformation to a digitalised, ecosystemic world simply has a huge impact also on the role and possibility of the university structures. It is no longer isolated to itself and its "building", the house of knowledge. No, in a ecosystemic world the higher educations, in order to follow the path of where society is heading, to be involved with other partners, the universities will have to function more in the same way. This in order to try things through prototyping and learn IRL. But also to learn by being in touch with others, with other competencies, which means both citizens and expertise from other fields of knowledge. In order to make this happen the university needs and can move out of its old comfort zone and drive the research IRL and try things, where for instance architects, engineers, financial expertise and citizens meet. That is when co-creation happens. Of course this does not go for all university faculties, but for architecture, design, certain engineering classes etc.

This opens up for yet another factor that has not been on the agenda: that areas outside of city centres, that can be far away from the academic institution, might have better circumstances for achieving relevant results: prices for land and property are lower, administration less complicated, the willingness to try might be larger. This means – better circumstances for prototyping, for testing, for research to meet reality.

So, it is smart to make connections with relevant academic institutions. Start a conversation. It might be the starting point of both innovative results and something that will be part of development processes also in other places, other regions, other countries.

THE PROBLEMS TO SOLVE

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A new set-up and a wider scope of both external factors (such as climate and democracy) require that old areas need to be solved in new ways, simply because the content is different because the challenges and needs tells us so. But they also need to be solved in dialogue with each other, in an – yes you know it by now – a way that could be described as ecosystemic. This circle in the Ecosystemic circle of 2023 is a short guide for you to be able start addressing, if not solving these problems.

INFRASTRUCTURE/MOBILITY

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The challenges were not there before. Cars and petrol used to be a given. As if it would always be there and as if it did not have an effect on the planet Earth.

This changed the face of cities and of the entire globe. Goods have since long now been transported across the globe, even fresh food. They still are. And cars have been and still are dominating our cities and our lives. To be able to move and travel, to connect, is not the same thing as using fossil fuel.

For many, especially on the country-side, cars has made life easier for many people. But with the ecosystemic transformation to a more locally based economy and democratic model, new possibilities open up. That can lead to pretty radical change, and still be done step-by-step.

Today, understanding that the system we have today cannot continue and we just cannot go on with the infrastructure solutions that we have had and mostly still have, open up for two things (both are already quickly being developed): inventing new solutions (smarter transportation etc) and restructuring what we have (using the roads, streets, railways, storage and public space differently).

So, here are a few things that can be good to keep in mind:

- Remind yourself that people don't like too radical changes, their everyday life cannot be too effected, which means that if something is taken away it has to be replaced by something else
- Remind yourself that there are innovations that can handle most problems that might occur (see below)
- On the countryside it is difficult to take away cars as a means to transport on a regional level, i.e. to other places than the one you live in
- Start with the idea of the local community and define the local centre
- Inside the local centre make a plan on how to reduce the amount of cars and transport radically
- To do this you need to plan the infrastructure so that at the entrances to the city centre that should be neighbourhood hubs
- This is where you have carpools, garage, storage and community food services – they will play an important part in the local community
- Try to fill the neighbourhood centres with creative life as well by adding studios for making and selling and trading
- This is where you could have part of the communal food centre (see below)
- Add smart local transportations (there is a huge number of innovative solutions, there should come several platforms where you can find the ones that suits you)
- You may still have buses etc in the centre of the local community
- What happens when you reduce traffic is that you open up for other activities, complementary use of streets and public space
- Invite the local business and citizens to plan these activities
- Add paths for walking, biking etc, also to the neighbourhoods close by, which will increase the use of non-car transpositions also for longer distances
- Add to the above as many new solutions as you may ever come up with

FOOD SYSTEMS

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Food is the ideal starting point for an updated societal development and action structure. Why? Because food systems are easy to understand, easy for everyone to see the problems with. Food is a basic human need, something that each and every human alive need every single day to stay alive, to say that food is cross generational is an understatement. And it is an industry that is and should be in radical transformation.

The transformation of food – which will be a key element in transforming to a greener and smarter societal structure – will not happen if not put in motion in a societal structure, if not part of an overall ecosystemic shift. And this is the new addition. Through innovative chefs like Douglas McMaster or Dan Barber (and many others) there is today a wider and wider knowledge of a possible new food system, that is circular, that is based on an impressive work to reach a zero waste system – which at the same time brings about delicious and healthy food.

Since many years the development of the food/tech innovations have prospered. Some with brilliant results. But there has been one thing lacking to really get the development process going: context.

Societal context. The chef's job is primarily to run a restaurant and make it profitable. The food/tech innovation companies are drilled to solve singular problems, because that is the way that the investment system works today. That has brought about some very smart companies. But they would be even smarter if tried on and tested through a local societal context. That is actually within the logic of the tech-oriented industries, to prototype, test, learn, adjust, retest, all in direct contact with end-users. The level of success would raise dramatically. Imagine a world with 100% success rate for start-ups! With a societal structure as a base and with AI comparison tools to use there is a far greater chance to reach sustainable and resilient goals for each and every partner involved.

The industrial idea of centralised production and distributions, of transporting fresh produce across the globe is a system that just doesn't work in a world of urgent climate crisis. It doesn't work with a digitalised and ecosystemic world either. If we transport tomatoes or fish across the globe (sometimes twice) to eat them fresh where they were once picked or caught, it is something that is severely wrong. So to reach a smarter, healthier food system on a local level, is key.

The questions posed are always the same: money, and costs. That the tomatoes that are travelling around the globe are cheaper for the customer. It is not true. A local chain for production, processing, distribution, supply and retail is not, by definition, something that will increase costs. On the contrary. But to decrease costs you need to create that famous ecosystem, so that several players interact and do it together.

Here's some "handbook" advise:

- First of all, the core of the ecosystemic world is smart collaboration and interaction. It is a system where different entities that used to be in competition, or a different sides of a table, see value created by collaboration of different sorts in order the cut costs and share ideas and make them better by bringing in the other players different expertise and experiences into the same game.

- That means, see the food system as a food system, not singular restaurants, kitchens, public food etc.
- The key factor in this is the local context, the local community; it is the tool to sharing, create values and to make new business at the same time as developing tools that will strengthen democracy.
- Gather all the players, preferably on the large aerial photograph on the floor and start defining how you can define a local food system, where there are plots of land to use, where there are kitchens that can be used for different, multiple purposes.
- Do not forget to bring in the citizens, because the citizens are both users/customers and possible producers.
- Do not forget to bring in digital tools, a contemporary local food system combines the artisanal with the digital in order to reach parallel goals: locally produced food that is healthier, more nutritious, more cost-efficient and that taste better.
- Create a local production chain. It is not as difficult as it might seem; find spots where you can grow food outdoors when it is season, plan how to do it, maybe there it could be run be local restaurants, maybe by the citizens – whatever solution it brings you local produce to low costs.
- Check how to establish and develop a business model for a common greenhouse.
- Bring in the local producers of meat and fish as well, or if there aren't any, see if you can find it nearby or if you can invite some to develop a business locally (as this movement continues to grow there will be new systems built that are going to be easier and easier to scale according to new contexts).
- Create a local supply-chain, where there are enough players with the same idea, again it is a bit like blockchain IRL.
- Create a local distribution chain, ideally where you connect individual citizens all the way to the larger players, like the local grocery store – and to aim at getting the large players on board.
- Create a local multi-use chain, where there are different use of for instance kitchens around the clock. This goes both for restaurant kitchens and public kitchens (in schools etc).
- Aim at making the local school food only made from local produce and food – if it is done in collaboration with restaurants it gives the restaurants extra income.
- Let the idea of learning through food systems and food production be an important part of the societal structure, as stated above there is a possibility with the schools and kids to learn about food that the pass on their parents.
- Aim at a new food culture.
- Aim at involving the elderly to take care of local smaller farms, that brings inclusion as well as cross-generational contacts, and food is perfect tool to achieve this.
- Aim at zero waste, there is a lot of knowledge and innovation within this field and, to be honest, it is again at field that is not hard to get going.
- Install common food system projects, like a compost that everyone in the neighbourhood use together.
- Install trucks that pick up food that would otherwise be thrown away.
- Make sure you have a kitchen (the school's?, or a mobile kitchen?) that can cook delicious food of what is picked up (several high-end chefs have introduced this idea, not least Massimo Bottura).
- Make sure that what you grow is connected to regenerative design processes and used for.
- Well, this is at least a brief starting point of the ecosystemic food system.

AFFORDABLE & SUSTAINABLE HOUSING

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The original Bauhaus circle by Walter Gropius aimed at creating new learnings and doings in the era of industrialism. In the early phase it generated ground-breaking results, both within architecture and design. The aftermath has, much later, caused a lot of problems and challenges that we now need to find new innovative solutions to come to terms with. The use of material, the use of resources, the methods that were great back then, turned out to be not so great over time. The UN predicted on March 20, 2023 that the 1.5 degree goal is not going to succeed. We simply need to accelerate the change.

To develop affordable and sustainable housing is an issue that urgently needs to be solved.

The need for shelter is a global challenge, that is getting even more urgent with global migration and climate changes. The extreme climates create urgent needs, often in unexpected ways. The war in Ukraine has showed that the need for affordable homes that are easy to build is on demand. This tells us that shelter is tightly linked to democracy and human rights. And that there is a need for temporary cost-efficient housing, which, in fact, should be a great opportunity to generate innovative new solutions.

With rising costs for housing in larger cities there is a big challenge also in prosperous cities. To keep the cities diversified there is also for this reason a need to build less expensive housing, that could even be temporary. There is simply a need for smart affordable housing to put alongside larger and more expensive constructions. Add-ons, rather than permanent and big.

We need to relearn. The industrial production is based on short term gains and nonreusable material. Now we have to go in the opposite direction.

Many innovative solutions are already here, or on their way. At architectural offices. At universities. At different labs and at new companies. With the right AI connections you can easily find ways to check what is being done. And you can refine and expand on existing ideas. There are many attempts and there are many innovative solutions to be found.

With expanding knowledge within regenerative material and robotic systems the production cycle of the ecosystemic societal development will be different from what it has been, smaller, flexible, moveable. Assembly units for housing that might be 200 square meters and right were you want to build.

Remember, the new generation of architects and designers are on to this, many of them are developing knowledge and ideas that are simply brilliant.

What is needed, just as in the case with the food systems, is the context, the canvas, the possibility to try, test and prototype, and to do so while considering all the other factors that need to be considered in an ecosystemic structure. The local scale is very suitable to test and prototype smaller units. And you should start there, in smaller scale. This is the way to have reasonable costs and budgets. But make sure to handle the IP early on.

- Set some very clear goals: zero waste, 100% regenerative impact.
- Prototype different specific questions in the initial phase.
- Start with a dialogue with the citizens on what is needed in all fields: housing, culture, people, social diversity, connections to existing housing etc.
- Do not just build houses, but do so in parallel with developing the local ecosystem with several other fields, like food, infrastructure, habitat.

- Co-create between the different players.
- Select architects to bring together the different expertise into a design.
- Do not forget to bring in energy systems as an innovative force.
- Set up a development test-site where you gather what is to do.
- make it into a regenerative site, bring materials there.
- Develop new up-cycled materials.
- Build a local assembly unit.
- One way to start is through temporary building permits, that can accelerate the process.
- Aim for simple solutions, but different for each house.
- Engage the civil servants to be part of the process, which can speed up the process and create communication locally.
- Invite architects to fulfil the ideas brought about through analysis of citizens wishes and through the context's possibilities.
- Think long-term development, so that what you build now should make way for other additions where you save costs.
- Use local construction and production, that is a smart, quick way to avoid industrial, linear processes that are expensive (and produce the usual stuff).
- Plan from the beginning to use the learnings from the first prototyping for coming construction.
- Believe in a tentative, agile process.
- Plan the garden, parking and storage from the perspective of reducing cars in the city centre.
- See if you can make all gardens productive so that they contribute to the food systems.
- Plan the housing units in relation to new business, temporary injections, local production.
- Plan for diverse use that is cross-generational.
- Challenge the industrial way of doing things by making it local and by staying at small scale.
- See the scaling as context-driven and on system level, not industrial.
- make new business models where everyone involved make money on the context-driven scaling.
- Create new business models at all stages, creative, co-creative, participatory, ownership.
- Generate new finance models with banks and foundations.

A PUBLIC HABITAT/SPACE

The legacy of the planning method from the industrial era is, as shown, based on specialised problem solving. It is based on a rational logic of planning where each and every function would be facilitated: traffic solutions, playgrounds, shopping, leisure, living, walking, age groups, and sports. Each activity and segment is within this logic planned with this in mind. That has deep roots in an entire era's very idea. You can basically look at any suburban area in Europa and you will notice the same phenomena.

The transformation to a digitalised society and an ecosystemic way of structuring society introduces a different approach. The specialised silos are being put in motion – out of necessity – to be in dialogue with the other specialised silos.

As we have seen this has an effect on everything in societal planning and has to be a gradual shift. But it has already been started. The very core of the ecosystemic way of working have a basic

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principles: to move away for silos and to begin the interaction between different entities. So when it comes to the habit of the local community you are working with, the neighbourhood or the village, this is the starting point, to put different functions and uses in contact and in dialogue and in an interplay between each other.

And with that follows another very important consequence. Within the old system the starting point for action was – for very good reasons – solving specific functions, like traffic or parking, parks, or pavements. That was how everything has been addressed.

It has produced functional habitats, different functionals functions in our public spaces. But the big issue today, that is currently being addressed, is the life in-between the functions, and in the interplay between the different functions. The starting point is thus something that could be describe with a very simple word, as "life" – the human being in the habitat, the citizen, and is thus a radical shift towards a participatory idea that has its base in democracy. Twisted positions. Not top-down. But ecosystemic.

With the life of the human – and other species – that live in a community it follows that the ecosystemic approach is how to connect, in-between the people that live in a local community, and how they can interact on a local basis. Not only to meet, but to bring value to the community, i.e. it has also a large potential of bringing everything from food to new business and culture to the community.

This is a different way of creating business than that of the old industrial era, where production and distribution has been based on large quantities and centralised construction and distribution.

We still need – more than ever – systems, structures, that can be applied and redeveloped with scale, but from the point of view of every specific place.

The idea of multi-use comes from digital possibilities, of smart system that bring efficiency, but also from the high costs in big cities. From the necessity of being able to pay very high rents, spaces, both indoor and outdoor, have come to be used for multiple functions. A building in a bigger city has a much better chance of surviving if it is used 24 hours, not only eight. That require a different kind of planning and thinking. Differences in the same physical space.

In terms of habitat and public space there is only a win-win situation in this. By starting the interplay between different functions, by focusing on local activities in the local community, you get a more lively habitat, more life in the city, and you also open for huge possibilities of local business development.

So, some basic ideas to develop an ecosystemic habitat and public space:

- As said, reduce the car traffic in selected, central streets, radically. It does not only head us toward a regenerative future, it open the street for multiple use.
- The local community and the local business will thus have an opportunity to make further business, through temporary activities, such as markets, on the street – that also has a social effect in bringing people together and generate attraction and communication as well as a sense of belonging.
- As you will see further down in this document, under the coming headline, this is the point where you generate synergies by opening up the physical community, it is to generate synergies.
- If you reduce the traffic in the centre areas you need to fulfil two things, one is to have garages and carpools at specific nodes that are close to the centre, to take away cars entirely and at once is going to create too much trouble, and by moving towards carpools you can update the cars.

- The second thing you need is smart local transportation. There are numerous innovative solutions out there, test and try in smaller scale before you decide, there are different needs according to climate and other physical circumstances.
- Also, take a look on storage and food storage, if that has a possibility to be added to the hubs for cars and transport. This has different potential in different countries and contexts.
- Parks in cities, especially larger, have a tradition of being though of a places of beauty, which is great. But bringing in some ideas from more rural contexts, they can also be part of the local community's local production, such as growing food, even other types of food.
- This, in conclusion, is why the habitat has to begin with the people, the human beings living in the community, and be a tool to generate common interests and purposes and thus be a tool for democracy.

CONTENT DEVELOPMENT

THE SYNERGY SYSTEM

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As you see by reading through the chapters of this "handbook", there is something simple that combines all the different areas. That is connecting. That is trying to bring about a puzzle where the different parts have a possibility to start interacting, play and create value by exactly this, interaction.

This is done through combining qualities from differences in a local community, together. It is a game that brings about more lively cities, that pave the way for a more sustainable and regenerative world, but also develop future local business.

We have lived in a world that had as an idea of separating entities, segments and knowledge. A world of not connected specialised fields of knowledge. We are now entering a world where differences are matched. We also need to move the world from centralised systems to decentralised local systems. Where the entire scope of the ecosystemic circle are put into motion.

To bring things together in a mutual system, thus generating an interaction in between different parties, is to start a game of synergies – and of generating efficiency as well as local business opportunities. But most of all, there is a possibility of bringing in life and engagement into a local community, by that very starting point.

- This is not coming out of the blue. The benefits of the tech-industries is that they have tested these models for years and in many cases disrupted old systems and made them more efficient and profitable. What the ecosystemic development suggest is to learn from that, apply it IRL and see how local communities can generate better environments to live in and to create more sustainable and resilient communities.
- So, the first thing you need to spend time on and have a budget for, is defining local possibilities and what you can actually achieve in order to generate an ecosystem that allows for future business while helping to create a regenerative world.
- (this should be a legal change, so that all projects have to have that initial process of defining the necessary questions to reach innovative and sustainable results).
- Define what, where, look for spots, get out on that aerial photograph.
- Define the process as well, define the vision.
- Spend time on this, refine the ideas.
- Set a really clear vision – like zero waste, a 100% regenerative societal local system, a local food system that is self-sustainable – and by having that goal in mind, start to lay out the bricks.
- Also set goals for business, that you want x amount of local companies to start (remember what we are doing is generating a new business model, the local and ecosystemic model).
- The food system is, as stated above, a great way to start, since it is easy to comprehend and easy to get moving.
- Do involve the big players, we are going to need big companies that can develop systems out of local systems, a different kind of scaling than that of the industrial principle, and remember that they are in need of this as well.
- The grocery store chains will probably be very interested in participating if you do this right.
- always add experts on tech and digital tools, that is how you will interact in between the players and that is how you will interact with the citizens, i.e. communicate.
- Add new additional housing to the food system, try to find ways of connecting production.

- Negotiate with local property owners to use vacant space for as little rent as possible to start activities, so that part of the funding is reducing costs.
- A regenerative principle is that what used to be separated now can be matched and put into play, so that the food system through a new generation of designers even can produce material and new products locally.
- Of course the use of infrastructure, of storage etc, will be part of the same game.
- Investigate how functions can be redistributed to better fit an ecosystemic societal development.
- Set up common functions, things that unite the people and make them interact, this is also smart to start with through the food systems.
- Make the local investment funds part of the synergy system, and be sure to add specialist within digital tools so that you can get things easy to communicate and so that you can see and filter data.
- Be transparent.
- Be productive.
- Involve the municipality directly, so that they are part of the synergy system, and you will need them to be part of the action and to be part of the legal system.
- Always be cross-generational, by involving young people and by involving older generations.

THE CREATIVE & PARTICIPATORY PROCESS

When Walter Gropius designed his famous circle for the education agenda at the Bauhaus School on 1922 it put a focus on a new generation of designers and architects. The new creative generation were set to be the tool to take the vision of the modern, industrial, democratic society and turn it into everyday objects as well as shelter and housing for the many. It was never about design as design, but about a social vision in a brave new world that needed design to come true. It was to design content. Not so few items of what they designed turned into be classics that inspired generations.

Today, when, as we see through the updated circle of 2023 there are many more layers to consider, much more knowledge to include, much more content, and a lot of that content is in the process.

Moving local and ecosystemic the participation of citizens and the interplay between different players is a very different starting point than that in 1922. In 1922 the designer or the architect, the creator, was in control of the entire process, as Gropius' circle diagram clearly illustrate. In 2023 that kind of control is impossible. There are too many people, too much knowledge to cross between players and industries. The co-creative part is a necessity, where you collect and bring in input from different sources, input that is vital also for the end result. It might be sustainability goals, it might be adapting to a local community and new businesses, it might be other aspects that will have a definite impact of the end result.

This gives the creative person a new role, initially as part of a participatory process, a process where many, of different kind, have inputs into what is to be designed or in some other way made into a creative statement. One is to be part of and often lead the process, or to curate it. Which means bringing all the players together and inject energy to get the most out of each and everyone.

The creative has different roles in the different stages of the process. In the beginning it could be to define the starting point and analyse context and vision, adjust to budgets and finance. A second phase is to work with the end-users, the citizens. A third (could be part of the same sequence) to bring in input from all the other fields of knowledge: business, sustainability, culture, all segments in societal context.

The input and the dialogue will definitely have an effect on the final result. So the designer designs the process but also collects the ideas and come with a proposal. Still design, and it important to have the creative mind come with the unexpected – but based on another kind of process. Then it might also include participatory elements, for instance if it is a building, where the citizens may be involved in the construction or the making.

To involve – early in the process – the creatives, is important. It could be local talent. It should be, to some extent. But it can also be creative people from other parts of the world. Remember that most creative people are triggered by an interesting proposal and context. Basically you can bring in anyone you want. But remember also that creative impact based on content development may be a key to the project's communicative effect. That is why you always need to bring in the creatives inside the entire process, to share the vision and the context, which is the needed challenge. They are there to solve problems and come with solutions that no-one else could think of.

That is the beauty of it all.

THE FORMS OF CITIZEN'S PARTICIPATION / DEMOCRACY

As was stated early, through the first circle of the diagram, the most urgent and important aspect in the transformation to an ecosystemic societal development is the democratic aspect. Democracy – and climate – are the two issues that the world simply need to deliver on. Quickly. And where an ecosystemic development in Europe can and should lead the way.

And, as said before many time, it does not have to be that difficult. But democracy is also part of the interactive ecosystem. It is more than that. It is the heart and core of the ecosystemic development.

It is not an isolated phenomena.

Read it again: democracy is not an isolated phenomena.

If you have this vision in front of your eyes, developing your local community, you will show that democracy is part of everything we do and how we do it, and that it is a human right, and one that is both engaging and connecting and fun.

Ask yourself what impact an updated model for societal development will have on how the citizens could be engaged in their own environments, their own neighbourhood's future, in their own participation of that future.

As shown in the different circles and segments there are a number of ways and keys to unlock the future of democracy. It is all about participation.

Start local

The local is the future

Don't make it difficult, activate your own surrounding

Invite the citizens to be part of creating the vision for the future of the neighbourhood.

The big vision, Make all players, also the citizens, to be responsible, both of the discussion and of the process.

This means that all parties are there on equal terms.

Set a process not only for a specific development, but long-term, to continue the process the local community and get the municipality to accept it and to in different ways make it legally sanctioned.

As stated several times in the "handbook", add investment funds, and create local innovation and collaborations with academia, so that both self-respect and jobs are created through.

By creating a circular economy you enter a circular democracy.

It is an ecosystemic democracy, a democracy based on interaction and doing in the local community.

Think of everything as local, everything you need, it is not better elsewhere.

The democracy with prosper through creating a local community.

Avoid to make the local democracy too attached to traditional political sides, try to find ways beyond opinion, baed on activity.

Have the circular and the zero waste as a starting point, because through that a lot of people will get involved.

Food is a tool, an important tool, to generate something that everyone can engage in.

Let people engage in the way that suits them, not everyone likes everything.

Culture is a tool. Find out how the local culture could be integrated into the process.

Find, as stated before, legal form, such as a company, that brings representatives from all sides, politics, business and citizens, and get a budget to have a flow workshop with the citizens.

Make sure that what comes out of the meetings have a reality-check and make sure that they then can be executed and done.

If you prototype you can test, testing in reality is to show action, which gives way for development

Bring in the municipality to see how they can be part of this, and gradually develop new habits, so that civil servants become enablers.

It is an ecosystemic transformation that starts with the local, with the neighbourhood, and the can move upwards.

The core of ecosystemic development is democracy.

REGENERATIVE DEVELOPMENT

Regenerative systems could be said to be a definition of an ecosystemic societal structure. Instead of waste, the very starting point of the regenerative system is to identify waste streams and then let them play a key role for an innovative reimagining of the future functions of today's society. That is why it is also key for any future "handbook" of societal development. If we want to achieve a society that will be 100% regenerative, this short chapter is meant to be an entry to a new and necessary way of thinking and acting.

The perception of waste must be challenged and redefined, resulting in a reduction of unnecessary waste globally. This inherently highlights the value of identified material by-products - i.e. waste - from businesses and how the utilisation of the material source can contribute to the growth of the business in which it originated by offering other forms of revenue.

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Our relationship to place plays a crucial role in restoring ecosystems and regenerating our communities. It is essential to listen to nature and take sustainable actions that benefit the environment, rather than exploit it. Choosing to listen to nature can help us restore ecosystems we're a part of - allowing our communities to thrive and grow. As designers, we can accelerate this process by changing the way we think and put design into practice. By doing so, we can create more sustainable and resilient communities that are better equipped to handle the challenges of the future.

Here lies many interesting opportunities:

- The utilisation of waste from commercial/public activities offer opportunities for businesses to reutilise the waste they produce and to generate further revenue streams as the burden of waste is eliminated and turned into regenerative materials.
- This means that new local businesses will come as a result of a local community turning regenerative
- It is a means of engagement for the citizens and thus part of generating a stronger local democracy
- Regenerative systems also mean regenerative ideas, where ideas are continually developed and are iterative.
- It is a way to open people's eyes and minds to look upon their own neighbourhood in a new way, filled with inherent opportunities.
- The idea of regenerative systems spans a broad range of disciplines from architecture & design through to food systems, but also on a human scale, from new business models to new engagement models the local community will play a strong role in the development of regenerative systems. There will be a strong connection to the place in which materials are identified, re- and upcycled.
- Each citizen has a possibility to feel engaged as a contributor to the local development of sustainability and thus becoming an integral partner of that location to contribute to its development, not just extract resources (physical & social) from that area.
- Regenerative systems seek to minimise and reduce the negative impacts and reducing harm that our activities have on the environment and society. Instead, it seeks to create systems and processes that actively restore, regenerate and renew the natural environment and the society/cultural fabric of the communities that it serves.
- Supply chains which are regenerative will always succeed since they are a constant source of materials. The regenerative system will be a core source for innovating the local community, to connect and to develop future business and resilience.

RETROFIT DEVELOPMENT

Retrofitting is to take care of existing buildings. Instead of tearing buildings down, a key to the future, especially in denser areas, will be to invest in retrofitting the existing buildings, so that they will be more efficient and resilient. This means an effort to update and up-cycle what we have – with much less damage to the existing city environment – and make what is already there more energy efficient, and enhance the seismic resistance of existing structures. It will reduce the carbon footprint to reach a 100% regenerative goal.

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Retrofitting is really to take care of what you already have by lowering energy costs, reducing maintenance requirements and creating value for those that already live in the building and the neighbourhood, so they can fit into the updated approach to zero-waste. It will be a key for future societal development since it will both keep what is and update to fit future and global needs. Working with existing systems and infrastructure to reduce their carbon footprint.

Retrofitting is truly Ecosystemic since retrofitting projects add new equipment, tech or building systems in order to improve the building, i.e. they combine the old with the new, the knowledge from before with that of the future.

Main principles:

- Energy efficiency, material health (important in the case of regeneration) and decarbonisation a commitment to all developments: low carbon. energy efficient, water efficient and climate resilient.
- This can be achieved through the installation of insulation, alternative energy systems and other alterations.
- Buildings and developments can also become more carbon neutral by improving the external systems such as transportation to and from the building. E.g. new bike routes, or upgrading public transport connections. Thus keeping traditions and skills alive, but making them contemporary to handle global challenges.
- It is a holistic approach to support all stakeholders, to motivate and facilitate changes can be delivered through a participatory and community driven practice, triggering a wave of action within communities, the country and even internationally.
- Maximise by connecting with communities, networks (business & public sector) and third party organisations.

INVESTMENT/INCUBATOR SYSTEM

To achieve a 100% regenerative human presence on planet Earth, collaboration across different knowledge silos is essential. We need to broaden our horizons, connect knowledge across industries in a circular manner, and agree on transparent open standards that enable us to share intellectual property and align incentives. Digital simulation technology can help us decarbonise our industries and transition all flows of matter to a circular model. However, to accomplish this, we need to redefine our approach to short-term monetary gains versus intergenerational wealth creation, prioritising long-term solutions.

To accelerate this process, we must create a shared digital simulation platform for planet Earth that encompasses a multitude of layers, touching on all aspects of the built environment. This platform should redefine how we share knowledge, design, co-create with end-users, and optimise for performance, challenging people to solve problems together and rewarding them for their contributions. By co-creating the solutions, we can ensure a circular and fully regenerative future.

As part of this effort, we should also establish a seed investor and incubator setup, a fund focused solely on building businesses that will help us decarbonise human presence on planet Earth. This

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initiative will bring together the best minds and solutions to create collaborative, scalable solutions that can be implemented to help decarbonise our industries.

This fund should provide the necessary resources and mentorship to help these businesses succeed and connect them with the world's leading investors to ensure that the best solutions can be prototyped and delivered at scale. To evaluate potential businesses, we need to develop a plan for monitoring and measuring the progress and impact of each one and providing feedback and guidance to help them refine and improve their products and services.

To validate each idea, we need to conduct a comprehensive review of the current research and patent landscape and conduct an in-depth analysis of the potential impact each business could have. We must also assess the financials, business model, competitive landscape, and team behind each company. Furthermore, we should consider the broader environmental and social impact of the business and its potential to scale in the future.

To support each business, this fund should provide access to capital, mentors, advisors, and industry experts. It should also help each business to find ways to prototype their ideas at scale. Finally, the fund should create a network of other investors, entrepreneurs, and industry experts who can provide support to the businesses they have invested in.

In conclusion, we must create a vibrant and sustainable ecosystem of entrepreneurs, investors, and innovators all working together to help decarbonise human presence on planet Earth. By collaborating across industries, we can develop scalable solutions that will pave the way for a circular and fully regenerative future.

INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY / DATA TRANSFER & SHARING SYSTEM

Collaboration across different knowledge silos is essential in achieving a 100% regenerative human presence on planet Earth. In this move towards circular solutions, it is crucial to team up all relevant professions and facilitate the co-creation of solutions across silos. Research has shown that connecting knowledge across industries in a circular manner can reveal the desired efficiencies and the most exciting opportunities for a sustainable future (Kirchherr et al., 2018).

To connect ideas and co-create solutions across industries, we need to agree on transparent open standards that enable us to share intellectual property (IP) and align incentives. Digital technology can also help us decarbonize our industries and move all flows of matter in a circular manner. However, the current practice of IP transfer needs fundamental innovation to maximize spin-off success. According to a study by Dicke et al. (2021), the traditional model of technology transfer is not suitable for co-financing research and teaching on a large scale, and patenting inventions is often costly and overall unprofitable. The traditional licensing model also does not fit knowledge-based spin-offs.

Virtual participation against assignment of IP rights has several advantages. It allows for easy transfer of IP rights to spin-offs, reducing transaction costs associated with traditional licensing models. It enables spin-offs to secure the necessary IP rights for their business operations without significant capital outflows in the startup phase. Finally, it facilitates the involvement of universities and

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research institutions in spin-off financing while co-financing research and teaching. According to a report by the European Commission (2020), clear legal provisions are required to ensure that all parties understand their rights and obligations under the model.

To make this a reality, we must align incentives and team up. Currently, only giant companies with many verticals under a single legal framework can explore synergies and discover efficiencies, but too often they lack the incentives and agility to drive innovation at scale. We need to build a sense of community that aligns our goals across industries, creates shared incentives, and assembles the world's best minds to drive innovation for a sustainable future (Hartmann et al., 2020).

Money is already moving towards sustainable solutions, and change is already happening. But we must accelerate the process by building 1:1 prototypes and living laboratories all around the planet to test possible solutions, share our learnings, and prepare the best solutions to scale (Friebe et al., 2021). Collaboration across different knowledge silos is obligatory to achieve a sustainable future. By aligning incentives, teaming up, and creating shared goals, we can build a sense of community that drives innovation for a regenerative human presence on planet Earth. Let's connect ideas, co-create solutions, and accelerate the process towards a truly sustainable, regenerative future.

ECOSYSTEM SYNERGIES

Action, prototype, do.

ACTION

PROTOTYPE

DO

ACTION

This is not what you do when all the rest, all the circles outside of the centre, is arranged. No, this part starts from the very beginning of the process. The very first glimpse of an idea is part of the action. All the rest that follows – it might be a process that will take ten years, or more – will be part of the same action, prototype and do. So, you already started. **PROTOTYPE**

Within the industrial logic prototyping is done in laboratories or separate test-units. When they are considered ready for the market, they are... put on the market, almost like a spaceship. If you want to produce relevance - establish an idea of working with prototyping as a means of moving forward. Prototype IRL. Prototype locally. Test, try and develop. Be sure to curate the process properly. And get a budget to set up the structure, where you need to create a collaboration between the different players: citizens, public and privat. By testing and prototyping IRL is a way to all the time

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generate engagement, democracy and business. And a way to save money while developing something that can, and most probably will, be used at other places as well. DO

Doing is believing. Believing is to know what you are doing. To know why, what and how. To understand context. To know is to figure out what you do not want to do. What is no longer relevant. To do so is to figure out the very that thing that you want to achieve by considering all the values added through analysing the updated, ecosystemic, circle in all layers, and then: do.

